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California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

OSTA VS. FRAX: PREDICTION OF OSTEOPOROSIS AMONG VIETNAMESE
AMERICAN WOMEN AGES 45-64

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

Donna Hong Tran

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN, Project Chair
Sue Robertson, PhD, RN Committee Member

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ABSTRACT

Osteoporosis affects 10 million people in the United States (U.S.), approximately 80% of which are women. This figure is estimated to rise to 14 million by 2020. The National Osteoporosis Risk Assessment found that Asian women living in the U.S. have higher rates of osteoporosis than do Caucasian women. One possible reason was that Asians had lower Bone Mass Density (BMD) at every age than other groups. While the current North American guidelines recommend that women 65 and older receive Dual Energy X-ray Absorptiometry (DEXA) for osteoporosis screening, they vary in specific recommendations for fracture risk assessment in women under 65. Evaluation of osteoporosis prescreening has not been well documented in postmenopausal Asian samples, particularly Vietnamese Americans.

This retrospective chart review aimed to compare the predictive values of two prescreening tools (Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asians, OSTA; Fracture Risk Assessment Tool, FRAX) for osteoporosis in Vietnamese born women ages 45 to 64 from a primary care setting in Southern California. The sample was 149 women who had a DEXA performed within the two prior years and received care from April 1 to October 2, 2018. Demographic and clinical risk factors were used to calculate scores for the OSTA and FRAX tools. To assess risk for osteoporosis, thresholds for the OSTA of ≤ -1 and the FRAX of $\geq 9.3\%$ were used. The BMD results of femoral neck (FN) and lumbar spine (LS) measured by DEXA obtained from Electronic Health Records. A BMD T score of

≤ -2.5 indicated a diagnosis of osteoporosis. A less conservative threshold of FRAX ($\geq 3.51\%$) was also used to compare with OSTA and FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$).

Using the FN measurement, the OSTA identified 32 of 48 women with osteoporosis and predicted 16 of 98 women to be without osteoporosis, resulting in sensitivity and specificity of 66.7% and 16.3%, respectively. For LS, OSTA identified 37 of 60 women with osteoporosis, predicting 24 of 81 women to be without osteoporosis, sensitivity and specificity of 61.7% and 29.6%. For both FN and LS, FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$) predicted no women with osteoporosis, resulting in sensitivity and specificity of 0% and 100%. Alternative threshold of FRAX ($\geq 3.51\%$) detected 28 of 77 women with osteoporosis, sensitivity and specificity of 36% and 100%.

In conclusion, neither OSTA nor FRAX predicted all DEXA results. Thus, an accurate prediction of fracture risk was not possible for Vietnamese postmenopausal women ages 45 to 64 in the project setting. However, OSTA, a simple tool based on BMI and age, had superior predictive value over FRAX in detecting fracture risk. This could be a major advantage to providers when choosing prescreening options and maximizing detection of osteoporosis. Using an alternative lower threshold of FRAX ($\geq 3.51\%$) would improve osteoporosis detection.

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BACKGROUND

Screening adult women for osteoporosis is inconsistent despite advances in radiological techniques and evidence-based screening guidelines. This means that women may not be diagnosed with osteoporosis, which is characterized as decreased bone mass and increased bone fragility (Buttaro, Trybulski, Bailey, & Sandberg-Cook, 2007). For the year 2000, worldwide, osteoporosis affected more than 200 million people, resulting in 8.9 fractures annually, or one new osteoporotic fracture every three seconds (World Health Organization, 2004a). More than half of these fractures occurred in Europe and the Americas, while most of the remainder occurred in Southeast Asian and Western Pacific regions (World Health Organization, 2004b). Of 8.9 million osteoporosis-related fractures, 1.6 million were hip fractures, with a potential incidence rate of 2.6 million by 2025, and 4.5 million by 2050 (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2009)

In 2002, osteoporosis potentially affected 10 million people in the United States (U.S.), with approximately 80% of those being women. This figure is estimated to rise to 14 million by 2020 (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2009). For postmenopausal women, osteoporosis-related fractures are more common than stroke, myocardial infarction and breast cancer combined (N. B. Watts & Manson, 2017). Osteoporotic fractures are prone to happen at the hip joints, lumbar vertebrae, and wrists (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2015a). Hip fractures are commonly associated with osteoporosis. Each year, over 300,000 older individuals suffer hip fractures with the majority of these resulting from falls (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016). Hip fracture incurs the highest medical costs for follow-up and treatment among all fractures (Christensen, Iqbal, Macarios, Badamgarav, & Harley, 2010). The cost of hip

fracture surgery was estimated at \$65,000 per patient, and the annual cost of hip fracture for persons age 65 and over is \$16 billion (American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons, 2014).

While most osteoporotic fractures occur in Europe and the Americas (World Health Organization, 2004a), it is predicted that in 2050 more than 50% of osteoporotic hip fractures will affect Asians (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2009). The 2010 U.S. Census showed that the Asian population grew fastest among all races in the U.S., and increased more than fourfold compared to the U.S. population between 2000 and 2010 (Hoeffel, Rastogi, Kim, & Shahid, 2012). The National Osteoporosis Risk Assessment found that for Asians living in the U.S, the rate of osteoporosis increased at the rate of 1.56 when compared to that for Caucasian women (Siris et al., 2001). Lower bone mass density (BMD) was reported among immigrant Chinese postmenopausal women living in Chicago, compared with that for White women and U.S. born Asian-American adults (Lauderdale, Kuohung, Chang, & Chin, 2003). A Vietnamese study using calcaneal quantitative ultrasound to determine BMD found that osteoporosis among women was highly prevalent when compared with that in the neighboring countries (Vu et al., 2005). Those results are consistent with evidence demonstrating that Asians had lower BMD at every age than other racial groups (Barrett-Connor et al., 2005).

Fracture is associated with increased risk of morbidity and mortality. The mortality rate among hip fracture patients during the first three months after fracture is up to four times greater than those of similar age and risk who do not sustain a fracture (Office of the Surgeon General [US], 2004). Left untreated, osteoporosis can have profound negative consequences on quality of life as well as medical costs due to diagnostic tests and

treatment. Health care practitioners must be aware of properly screening patients facing high risks for osteoporosis. Many guidelines and prescreening tools for osteoporosis were developed using Caucasians (Chen et al., 2016). Evaluation of osteoporosis prescreening, however, has not been well documented in postmenopausal Asian population, particularly Vietnamese American women. Therefore, the aim of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to identify appropriate prescreening tools for Vietnamese women living in US, and to determine if they predict women who should receive screening for osteoporosis.

Problem Statement

Osteoporosis is preventable if caught early, and treatable through proper detection and early intervention. The diagnosis of osteoporosis is based on the identification of risk factors and estimates of BMD through using advanced radiological techniques (Masi, 2008). The current gold standard to measure BMD is dual energy X-ray absorptiometry (DEXA). The cost of using DEXA to assess BMD is high; therefore, it is often not reimbursed by insurance companies for younger postmenopausal women (World Health Organization, 2004b). As a result, many professional organizations have provided guidelines for osteoporosis screening. Current North American guidelines, including American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists (AACE), the US Preventive Services Task Forces (USPSTF), the National Osteoporosis Foundation (NOF), the North American Menopause Society (NAMS), and Osteoporosis Canada Guidelines, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Recommendations of Professional Organizations for Osteoporosis Screening

Professional organization	Who should be screened	Screening strategy
AACE (N. Watts et al., 2011)	Women 65 and older Peri- or post-menopausal women with fracture risks Individuals with secondary osteoporosis	DEXA
USPSTF (U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), 2011)	Women 65 and older Younger women with fracture risks	DEXA
NAMS (North American Menopause Society, 2010)	Women 65 and older Postmenopausal women with a disease-causing bone loss or a fragility bone Younger women age 50 and older with fracture risks	DEXA
NOF (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2008)	Women 65 and older and men 70 and older Younger women and men 50-70 with fracture risks Individuals sustaining a fracture after age 50 Individuals suffering a medical condition or taking a drug that causes bone loss Postmenopausal women discontinuing estrogen	DEXA
2010 Osteoporosis Canadian Guideline (Papaioannou et al., 2010)	Women and men 65+ Women age 50-64 with fragility fracture after age 40 or with fracture risk Women under 50 with fragility fracture, premenopause (age < 45), or with fracture risks	DEXA

Notes. AACE = American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists; DEXA = dual energy X-ray absorptiometry; NOF = National Osteoporosis Foundation

Despite the guidelines, screening rates for osteoporosis are low and vary among eligible women. It is clear that women 65 and older should receive DEXA. However, younger women are determined eligible for DEXA by having non-age-related risk factors for osteoporosis. Even so, women 60 and over with one or more risk factors were found as having been screened and treated at a rate of only one in three in a primary care setting (Hamrick, Cao, Agbafé-Mosley, & Cummings, 2012). Another study revealed that only 62.6% of women and men aged 60 and older with additional risk factors for fracture reported being screened for osteoporosis (Smita Nayak, Roberts, & Greenspan, 2009).

On the other hand, approximately 40% of postmenopausal women 49 and older receive unnecessary DEXA scans (Schnatz, Marakovits, DuBois, & O'sullivan, 2011). In one study, about half of women under age 65 without fracture risks received bone density testing during a 7-year period (Amarnath, Franks, Robbins, Xing, & Fenton, 2015). According to American College of Physicians (ACP), the 2013 national rate of potential overuse for DEXA scan in women under age of 65 was 35%, as compared to 27% for all unnecessary health care services (American College of Physicians, 2016). These findings indicate that screening for osteoporosis by clinicians is inconsistent and can be either excessive or not done.

Purpose Statement and Objectives

The aim of this DNP project is to improve screening in order to support appropriate DEXA scans and identify osteoporosis cases among postmenopausal women 45 to 64 years in a multi-practitioner primary care setting located in Orange County, California. In order to complete this change in practice, project aims are:

- 1) Examine a sample of Vietnamese *post*-menopausal women, age 45 to 64, who have already received the DEXA-based BMD test and had appointments at the clinic between April 1, 2017 and October 2, 2017
- 2) Compare the ability of two risk factor based-osteoporosis screening tools against the BMD test to identify osteoporosis.
- 3) Share results of the DNP project with Health Care Practitioners (HCP) regarding the use the evidence-based screening tool for patients at risk for fractures.

Significance of the Project

Ultimately, HCPs need help to discriminate among postmenopausal women with or without risk factors for osteoporosis in order to appropriately order DEXA. The implementation of an effective prescreening instrument would assist clinicians in decreasing the numbers of unnecessary DEXA scans. The prescreening instrument may increase the percentage of women who are candidates for risk-based osteoporosis screening using DEXA. Use of the instrument should thus lead to appropriate age-based screening for osteoporosis, and when coupled with appropriate treatment, reduce health care costs related to osteoporosis.

Currently, prescreening of postmenopausal women ages 45 to 64 within the clinical setting for this project occurs inconsistently across practitioners. Some HCPs randomly order BMD tests (DEXA) that may not have been supported by evidence. The main reason for the practice inconsistency is lack of awareness regarding risk-based criteria for screening. As seen in Table 1, there are evidence-based screening guidelines for osteoporosis; however, the literature is limited regarding whom to screen for osteoporosis in *post*-menopausal Vietnamese American women who are under 65 years.

Supporting Framework

The framework selected for this doctoral project was the integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (i-PARIHS). The i-PARIHS model equates successful implementation with a complete integration of the interrelational function of innovation, recipients, context, and facilitation (Figure 1) (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). This framework provides guidance on how to diagnose crucial components related to evidence-based practice (EBP) interventions (innovation, recipients, and context), and

thence develop an implementation strategy (facilitation) to effectively make successful changes happen (Stetler, Damschroder, Helfrich, & Hagedorn, 2011).

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
What the Facilitator Does

Figure 1. The integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (i-PARIHS) model.

Innovation Construct

The *innovation* construct is the modified evidence construct from the original PARIHS framework. Innovation is the exploration of factors that influence the translation of knowledge into practice. The characteristics of the innovation encompass the underlying sources of knowledge, clarity, compatibility with existing evidence, degree of fit and usability, problem identification, and stakeholder mapping (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). In other words, the innovation, when combined with a number of different

determinants of knowledge translation, will inspire decision-making within the practice setting (Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

Recipient Construct

Recipients are the people who have direct influence on or are affected by the intervention of the change. These recipients can either support or resist the innovation at both the individual and collective-team level as illustrated in Figure 1 (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Successful implementation of change is more likely to occur when evidence is well conceived and agreed upon as compelling among involved individual recipients (Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

Context Construct

The *context* is the location or situation in which the innovation or change is to be implemented. Within the i-PARIHS framework, the context is distinguished as either inner or outer. The *inner context* involves the local and organizational levels in which the recipients work. The local level comprises formal and informal leadership, support, evaluation, and feedback processes. The organizational level includes organizational priorities, stakeholder engagement, policies, and procedures. The *outer context* comprises the wider health system that influences the inner context. It includes external policies (e.g., guidelines from professional organizations), regulations, healthcare system, and political infrastructures (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Facilitation Construct

Facilitation is the skills used to increase the likelihood that a goal will be effectively implemented and promoted (Kitson, Harvey, & McCormack, 1998). In the i-PARIHS framework, the success or failure of an innovation is determined by the ability of

the facilitators to implement it within the appropriate context (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

The role of facilitators can range from a specific task of supporting a change to a more complex, multifaceted duty (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Facilitators can be either internal or external to the organization, or a combination of both (Brown & McCormack, 2005).

The Model

The i-PARIHS framework is illustrated as a continuous spiral which starts with an innovation and recipients involved with it and moves toward different layers of context (Figure 1). The spiral shape reflects the facilitator's levels of experiences. Novice facilitators are more likely to lead a local implementation of a project while more experienced facilitators can assess more complex barriers or contextual factors influencing the project goal (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Application of the i-PARIHS Framework into the Project

This doctoral project aimed to improve the identification of women at risk for osteoporosis in a primary care setting. The DNP candidate was the novice facilitator. Upon finding that a prescreening instrument was effective in predicting osteoporosis, she will work with others in the work setting, who may or may not be actually more experienced in facilitation – to ensure the instrument will be implemented.

The need for the innovation stems from knowledge about osteoporosis prevalence and current screening inconsistency among Vietnamese American women at the primary care setting. Recommendations from existing national clinical guidelines for screening the population at risk for osteoporosis were analyzed and synthesized. Published evidence was reviewed to identify osteoporosis screening tools appropriate for the population and determine the factors affecting screening compliance (which may involve both the patient

recipients and the HCP recipients). Given the evidence found, the facilitator and other stakeholders (recipients) will consider whether the introduction of the planned osteoporosis screening guideline is congruent with clinic provider experiences as well as population needs.

The target recipients for the project's practice change are the HCP team members (e.g., providers, staff, managers) and patients. At the individual level, the course of implementing the innovation or change can be either furthered or impeded by the perceptions and attitudes of these team members. The facilitator will work with the team members regarding the new change, in order to explore motivation, values, and beliefs. Each team member's ability to change in relation to the innovation will be gauged. Based upon prior conversation with HCPs at the clinic, it is known that some providers do not believe screening and treatment of osteoporosis is necessary; these HCPs believe that decreased bone density is part of the natural process of aging and that screening and treatment will only cause anxiety for patients already suffering from multiple illnesses.

Patient knowledge regarding risks and benefits of osteoporosis disease also influences the implementation of the innovation. Since the implementation of the proposed screening instrument will be adopted across the primary care setting, patient awareness of screening will change when providers and other members of the team perceive the change valuable and worthwhile in decreasing hip fractures.

The primary care setting is the context in which the proposed implementation (screening instrument) will be introduced. Several contextual factors are important to consider. At the local level, inconsistency in use of the screening tool among postmenopausal women was found in a 2016 evaluation of practice. Some HCPs were

unaware of evidence-based screening guidelines; therefore, they might have missed opportunities for early detection of osteoporosis. During the introduction of the new osteoporosis screening guideline, the facilitator will need to assess opportunities and barriers among providers and staff for putting the guideline into practice. Providers are more likely to be supportive of the proposed guideline recommendation if this will decrease unnecessary DEXA scanning. This, in turn, will improve performance review incentives within the organization. The ultimate project purpose is to have appropriate screening and treatment of osteoporosis in women ages 45-64, which should prevent osteoporosis-related fractures. At the organizational level, engagement among the more experienced facilitators and key stakeholders in implementation of innovations should be evaluated.

The DNP facilitator will seek the support and guidance from management for implementing any new policies and procedures for osteoporosis screening, establishing referral monitoring systems, and embedding new recommended practices into the EHR system. Mandatory training and education will be provided to improve the required skills of the staff for implementing the new guideline. Provider meetings will be scheduled monthly to share and support this newly established protocol as well as monitor compliance osteoporosis screening rates. Most importantly, feasibility issues such as times, cost, and needed resources pertaining to the implementation of new change will be assessed throughout the project.

Also, important to the project is awareness of factors in the outer context including coverage by health insurance plans for osteoporosis screening and treatment, continuing professional education for providers, and public osteoporosis screening awareness

outreach campaign. The DNP facilitator will use more experienced facilitators to explore the wider range of activities outside the organization that may impact the project's goal. Working with the more experienced facilitators, the novice facilitator will develop skills learning how to become more familiar in health care policy and political influences in taking the evidence into practice. Consequently, the innovation implementation should lead to a change in practice that results in improved patient care.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This literature review began with a comprehensive search of the following computerized databases: PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, ScienceDirect, and PsycINFO, and Google Scholar. Evidence for the following topics was sought: (a) osteoporosis, (b) osteoporosis prescreening instruments among postmenopausal women, (c) determinants of screening inconsistencies, and (d) Asian and Vietnamese samples.

The search results were reviewed for inclusion and exclusion criteria using two steps, examining the titles and abstracts followed by review of the full text, in order to gather relevant studies. Articles from the first search were included if they evaluated the performance of osteoporosis screening tools for identifying osteoporosis risk among postmenopausal women. Publications were excluded if they focused on diagnostic tests (e.g., ultrasound, computerized axial tomography (CT) scan, and DEXA scan), medications, education, and special populations (e.g., diabetes, renal disease, liver disease, and autoimmune disorder). For the second search, articles were selected if they reported on factors and determinants of screening for osteoporosis. Studies were excluded if they did not describe barriers or compliance in osteoporosis prevention.

Bone Health Assessment

The assessment of bone health begins with understanding what bone is made of and its structure. Bone structure consists of bone cells, extracellular organic and non-organic components. Bone cells are comprised of osteocytes, osteoblasts, and osteoclasts. Osteocytes regulate bone remodeling, whereby the activity of osteoblasts and osteoclasts is stimulated or inhibited. Osteoblasts are responsible for bone formation, while osteoclasts modulate bone resorption. An imbalance in regulation of osteocytes,

osteoblasts and osteoclasts can lead to decreased bone mass density, with altered quality or quantity (Buehring, Viswanathan, Binkley, & Busse, 2013). These skeletal abnormalities are classified as osteoporosis (Buttaro et al., 2007).

Osteoporosis is categorized as two forms of bone turnover: low bone turnover or high bone turnover (Unnanuntana, Gladnick, Donnelly, & Lane, 2010). Low-turnover osteoporosis is characterized by a decrease in both bone formative and resorptive activities. This results in failure to maintain an appropriate level of bone matrix (Boskey, DiCarlo, Paschalis, West, & Mendelsohn, 2005). Conversely, high-turnover osteoporosis is an increase in loss of bone due to rapid osteoclastic activity. This occurs regardless of the degree of osteoblastic activity. With either low or high turnover, the rate of bone resorption or removal of mature bone tissue usually surpasses the rate of bone formation or bone remodeling that occurs in younger bone matrix. In other words, bone loss occurs at a much faster rate than bone growth. This imbalance of bone turnover causes osteoporosis (Boskey et al., 2005).

High-turnover osteoporosis often occurs in postmenopausal women, or in individuals with hyperparathyroidism. Low-turnover state is common among the elderly or among patients who undergo pharmacological treatments including corticosteroids, chemotherapy, and the long-term use of bisphosphonate medications. Distinguishing the form of bone turnovers can help in the assessment for efficacy of osteoporosis treatments among various patient populations (Unnanuntana et al., 2010).

Clinical Risk Factors

The causes of osteoporosis are multifactorial with some being modifiable and others not. Unmodifiable factors include older age, female, postmenopausal status,

ethnicity (White, Asian, and Hispanic), and heredity (Kaczkowski & Frey, 2013). In the first few years post-menopause, estrogen deficiency contributes to 1% to 5% of bone loss per year. Bone loss continues to occur throughout the remainder of a woman's life, accelerating after age 75 (Andreoli, Carpenter, Griggs, & Benjamin, 2007). Age and sex are strong determinants of osteoporosis risk. The prevalence of osteoporosis increases with age in women after age 50 and in men after age 80, and is more predominant among women (16%) than among men (4%) (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2015). Osteoporosis affects all ethnic and racial groups; however, White women experience hip fractures almost twice more than White men, and suffer the highest hip fracture rate among all ethnicities, followed by Asians and Latinos (Cauley, 2011).

Heredity plays a significant role in the prediction of osteoporosis. Genes responsible for bone mass density are found linked with genes which regulate estrogen, calcitonin receptors, and vitamin D (Zofkova, 2011). Family-based studies demonstrated the relationship between heredity and estimates of BMD, with twin studies demonstrating that heredity and BMD are linked between 50% and 85% (Stewart & Ralston, 2000). Similarly, specific genes were found to be significantly associated with BMD and risk for osteoporosis among Han Chinese postmenopausal women (Zhang et al., 2015). Based upon this evidence, family history of fracture (which indicates likely osteoporosis) has become an important clinical risk factor in assessing osteoporosis risk.

Modifiable clinical risk factors include low body mass index (BMI), current use of glucocorticoid therapy, smoking and alcohol use, decreased calcium and vitamin D intake, inadequate physical activity, certain medications, and certain diseases (Kaczkowski & Frey, 2013). Individuals with low body weight and small bone frame are at greatest risk of

osteoporosis (National Institute of Health, 2014). In a prospective cohort study, women with BMI of 20 kg/m² were found to have lower BMD two to four years after menopause, compared with those with BMI of 30 kg/m² or higher who take 5-9 years (Saarelainen et al., 2012). This result is consistent with another study which showed that a BMI of less than 28 kg/m² is a strong predictor of osteoporosis (Jiang, Good, Spinka, & Schnatz, 2016).

Glucocorticoid therapy adversely affects bone strength and quality.

Glucocorticoids decrease bone formation and remodeling while increasing bone resorption (Buehring et al., 2013; Henneicke, Gasparini, Brennan-Speranza, Zhou, & Seibel, 2014). Individuals are at greater risk of hip and vertebral fractures when receiving prednisone equivalent dose of 10 to 12 mg per day for more than three months. Therefore, intake of glucocorticoids is considered a clinical risk factor for fractures (Buehring et al., 2013).

Lifestyles can affect the incidence of osteoporosis. Both impact and non-impact exercise are positively associated with high bone mass in pre- and post-menopausal women (Tatsuno et al., 2013). Moreira and colleagues (2014), examining different kinds of activities on bone metabolism of postmenopausal women, showed that impact exercise (walking, weight lifting) stimulated bone tissues. Similarly, whole body vibration had positive effects on bone remodeling and formation (Moreira et al., 2014; Weber-Rajek, Mieszkowski, Niespodziński, & Ciechanowska, 2015). Alcohol negatively affects bone health. An alcohol intake of more than 30g of pure alcohol per day increases risk of fracture (Tatsuno et al., 2013). A cross-sectional study among Korean postmenopausal women showed lower BMD of alcohol drinkers as compared to that of abstainers (Seo, Chun, Newell, & Yun, 2015). Asian women are more susceptible to alcohol-related

fracture risk due to much lower body weight and height than those seen in Western countries (Tatsuno et al., 2013)

Secondary causes of osteoporosis are responsible for about half of osteoporosis cases in premenopausal women. The secondary causes include certain medications (i.e., glucocorticoids, chemotherapy, heparin, anticonvulsants, high dose levothyroxine) and certain conditions (i.e., rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease, liver disease, kidney disease, anorexia) (McLendon & Woodis, 2014). Therefore, most of the professional organizations recommend osteoporosis screening for persons who take these medications or suffer from these conditions (see Table 1).

Chemical Factors Influencing Osteoporosis

Vitamin D or 25-hydroxyvitamin (25-OH) D plays an essential role in the prevention of osteoporotic fractures by stimulating gastrointestinal calcium absorption which supporting bone mineralization by allowing adequate serum calcium/phosphate concentrations (National Institute of Health, 2016). Vitamin D is made through photosynthesis. Unfortunately, older individuals lose ability to convert sunlight into vitamin D through skin, which can lead to vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency (Andreoli et al., 2007). Few foods contain vitamin D naturally and very small amounts of vitamin D are found in these foods. Therefore, vitamin D is widely available in forms of supplements and fortified foods (National Institute of Health, 2016).

While serving as a biomarker, serum (25-OH) D concentration does not exactly correlate with amounts in body tissues and is not a perfect proxy for bone health (National Institute of Health, 2016). The USPSTF does not support screening for vitamin D deficiency among asymptomatic patients (U.S. Preventive Services Task Force, 2014).

However, different professional organizations recommend screening (25-OH) D levels for bone health. One study indicated that having (25-OH) D serum levels between 70 to 80 nmol/L decreases the likelihood of fracture risks (Dawson-Hughes et al., 2005). The Endocrine Society recommends that the serum (25-OH) D levels of 30 ng/ml and above should be maintained (Holick et al., 2011). To reach this level, experts from the International Osteoporosis Foundation (IOF) recommended that seniors aged 60 years and older take at least 800-1000 I.U. per day of vitamin D (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2015a). Vitamin D deficiency is prevalent globally; serum (25-OH) D levels below 25 nmol/L are widespread in South Asian and Middle Eastern countries and are linked with higher risk for fracture (Mithal et al., 2009).

A major structural component of bone tissues, calcium is also vital in preventing fractures. The recommended daily calcium intake for postmenopausal women aged 51 years and older is 1200 mg (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2015b). However, calcium intake is often not optimal among all population. A study conducted on South Asian women in Dallas Metroplex found that a majority did not meet recommended calcium allowances in their diet and showed a poor knowledge of calcium in preventing osteoporosis (Shakil et al., 2010).

Symptoms of Osteoporosis

Osteoporosis is considered a silent disease because it exists for a long time without causing pain. Common symptoms of osteoporosis include a decrease in height, bent-over posture due to compression of vertebral bones, and fragility fractures. Fragility fractures usually occur at the hips, lumbar spine, and wrists (Kaczkowski & Frey, 2013). However, osteoporosis can go unrecognized for years until a fracture occurs. There is no correlation

between neck, arm, and back pain and a diagnosis of osteoporosis (Zhao, Liu, & Zheng, 2013).

Diagnosis of Osteoporosis

Osteoporosis can be assessed by measuring biochemical markers of bone turnover. There are two types of biochemical bone markers: bone resorption and bone formation. These markers can be measured through blood and urine samples. Bone loss is measured through the increase in levels of bone resorption markers (Unnanuntana et al., 2010). Compared with BMD testing and clinical risk factors, biochemical bone marker values are equally useful for assessing future fracture risks and selecting appropriate drug therapy (Nishizawa et al., 2013). Moreover, biochemical bone markers are reflective of the whole-body skeletal bone loss and more accurate than BMD measurements. The BMD measurement specifically measures metabolic rates at local body sites (Delmas, Eastell, Garnero, Seibel, & Stepan, 2000). However, the use of biochemical markers are less applicable in clinical care settings due to (a) lack of tissue specificity to bone, (b) difficulty with interpreting results due to co-existing chronic diseases such as renal failure, diabetes, and use of certain medications, and (c) fluctuations in chemical values which can change over short periods of time causing difficulties in osteoporosis management (Cavalier et al., 2016).

In 1994, WHO established osteoporosis as a condition based on the estimation of BMD. The BMD test values, called *t*-scores, were compared with those of healthy non-Hispanic white adults, age 20 to 29, living in the U.S. (J. A. Kanis et al., 2008). The DEXA scan is the most commonly used measurement of BMD. However, due to its inconvenience, cost, and low sensitivity when screening individuals with increased risks

for fracture, it is not widely used (World Health Organization, 2004a) although use has increased with guideline awareness. Also, identifying osteoporosis by BMD alone does not capture all individuals at high risk for fractures. Persons without osteoporosis diagnosis can experience a hip fracture, and those with osteopenia who suffer a fracture of vertebrae, proximal humerus, or pelvis can be classified as having osteoporosis (Siris et al., 2001). Consequently, osteoporosis is no longer diagnosed as a skeletal disease based solely upon low BMD (Unnanuntana et al., 2010). In the 2004 WHO summary report, a revised assessment of osteoporosis and osteopenia were described; these include use of selected factors for identifying risk of fractures (World Health Organization, 2004a) (see Table 2). Evidence now supports osteoporosis as being diagnosed based on individual's probability of fractures rather than on BMD score alone (International Osteoporosis Foundation, 2015a).

Table 2

Diagnosis for Osteoporosis Based on 2004 WHO criteria

Diagnosis	DEXA- scan <i>t</i> -score
Normal	-1 or greater
Osteopenia	-1 to -2.4
Osteoporosis	-2.5 or lower
Severe osteoporosis	-2.5 or lower with one or more osteoporosis risk factors

Note. WHO = World Health Organization; DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry

Osteoporosis Prescreening Instruments

Use of clinical risk factors can provide some discriminative value in predicting fractures. In other words, the use of risk assessment instruments in conjunction with BMD predicts fracture probabilities to a greater extent than BMD alone (J. Kanis et al., 2007).

Since the 1990s, several risk assessment tools have been established to qualify patients for the BMD test, reducing the number of unnecessary DEXA scans among individuals at low risk for fracture (Schwartz & Steinberg, 2006).

In a systematic review (Rubin, Friis-Holmberg, Hermann, Abrahamsen, & Brixen, 2013), authors identified 48 osteoporosis risk assessment tools. Of these, 20 had external validity but only six were evaluated in community settings and met a sufficient quality of methodological approach. These six are the Fracture Risk Assessment (FRAX), the Simple Calculated Osteoporosis Risk Estimation (SCORE), Osteoporosis Self-Assessment (OST) (OST also known as the Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool in Asians [OSTA]), the Osteoporosis Risk Assessment Instrument (ORAI), Garvan Fracture Risk Calculator (GARVAN), and Quality Assessment Tool for Diagnostic Accuracy Studies (QUADAS).

Each instrument focuses on different fracture risk factors, along with different ages for optimal initiation for treatment, and thresholds for selection of initiation treatment (Smita Nayak, Roberts, & Greenspan, 2011; Schwartz & Steinberg, 2006). None consistently sustains superior performance over the others. However, quick and uncomplicated tools requiring fewer risk factors (i.e., OST/OSTA, ORAI, GARVAN) often perform as well or more than do more complex tools (i.e., SCORE, FRAX, QUADAS) (Rubin et al., 2013). Several studies have found that OST/OSTA is quick, simple and effective for identifying osteoporosis among younger postmenopausal women (Crandall, 2015; Lu, Chen, Cai, & Wei, 2006; McLeod & Johnson, 2009; Yang et al., 2013). On the other hand, FRAX, a more complex osteoporosis assessment tool, reduces unnecessary DEXA scans for women age 50-64 (Crandall, 2015; Edwards, Grover, Cook,

& Chang, 2014) (see Appendix A, Table 1). Moreover, FRAX scores rely on easily obtainable clinical information (i.e., age, weight, persona, social and family histories) (Centre for Metabolic Bone Diseases, n.d.). Therefore, the USPSTF recommends using FRAX to estimate 10 year fracture probability in women ages 50 to 64 (U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), 2011).

OSTA as Prescreening Tool

The OSTA tool was developed by WHO using data from postmenopausal Asian women in eight Asian countries, and is based upon age and weight (Koh et al., 2001). Since OSTA was developed, many studies have evaluated its performance for identifying primary osteoporosis among postmenopausal women. Authors of three meta-analysis examining sensitivity and specificity of various instruments (Crandall, 2015; McLeod & Johnson, 2009; S Nayak, Edwards, Saleh, & Greenspan, 2015) have concluded that it is a quick, simple, consistent tool for prediction of low BMD in multiple countries.

In evaluation of performance of ORAI, SCORE, and OST/OSTA tools (Gourlay et al., 2005), Gourlay and colleagues concluded that these three tools yielded similar accuracy of diagnosis but the sensitivity of the OST/OSTA (89.2 %) in women ages 45-64 years was higher than SCORE and ORAI (88.5%). In contrast, Ahmadzadeh and colleagues (2013) showed that SCORE had the highest sensitivity (95%) whereas OST/OSTA yielded the highest specificity (71.4%) (Ahmadzadeh, Emam, Rajaei, Moslemizadeh, & Jalessi, 2014). In another study, Crandall et al. (2015) demonstrated that OST/OSTA and SCORE were superior to FRAX in detecting women with osteoporosis having $t\text{-score} \leq -2.5$. Three individual studies compared different tools for

identifying osteoporosis on postmenopausal Asian women ages 55 years and over by utilizing the results of the sensitivity and specificity of each tool (see Table 3).

Table 3

Sensitivity and Specificity of Prescreening Tools in Assessing Risks of Osteoporosis in Asian Women

Authors	Prescreening tools	Sensitivity %	Specificity %
Muslim et al. (2012)	OSTA < -1	87.5	95.8
Cheung et al. (2014)	FRAX \geq 9.3%	22.6	47.2
Chan et al. (2006)	SCORE \geq 6	89	50
Chan et al. (2006)	ORAI \geq 9	97	41.3

Note. OSTA = Osteoporosis Self-Assessment in Asian; FRAX= Fracture Risk Assessment; SCORE = Simple Calculated Osteoporosis Risk Estimation; ORAI = Osteoporosis Risk Assessment Instrument

The OSTA had the highest specificity for identification of osteoporosis among postmenopausal Asian women. Moreover, the OSTA is the only instrument that evaluated the risk of osteoporosis among only Asian women. It was based solely on body weight and age, whereas other instruments (SCORE, FRAX, ORAI) include age and weight along with other clinical risk factors (Muslim, Mohd, Sallehudin, Muzaffar, & Ezane, 2012).

The factors of age and weight were sufficient when evaluating Asian women for osteoporosis. Advanced age and lower body weight are consistently concomitant with high risk for fracture (Koh et al., 2001). One systematic review (Waugh et al., 2008) and a study (Jiang et al., 2016) found similar results regarding risk factor of low body weight as significant predictor for osteoporosis among young postmenopausal women.

FRAX as a Prescreening Tool

The FRAX, the most sophisticated osteoporosis assessment tool, was developed by the University of Sheffield in connection with the WHO using samples from North

America, Europe, Australia, and Asia. Launched in February 2008, the FRAX calculator can be accessed at: <https://www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/tool> (University of Sheffield, 2017).

The aim of FRAX is to provide the prediction of increased fractures based solely on risk factors or with the femoral neck BMD (Unnanuntana et al., 2010). The FRAX estimates the individual's 10-year probability of fracture, and 10-year probability of a major osteoporotic fracture. It has been widely validated and is considered applicable in different population-based settings including the U.S., China, Japan, and several European countries (World Health Organization, 2007). The NOF recommends using FRAX for treatment of osteoporosis in individuals who meet the following criteria: (a) postmenopausal women or men ages 50 and over, (b) people with low BMD, and (c) people who have not received treatment of osteoporosis (National Osteoporosis Foundation, 2017). The USPSTF recommends FRAX threshold of 9.3% to prescreen women age 50 to 64 for osteoporosis (U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), 2011)

Several studies have focused on the performance of FRAX for identifying primary osteoporosis among postmenopausal women. Two studies found that the FRAX threshold of 9.3% for detecting major osteoporotic fracture (MOF) had a low sensitivity (33.3%-36%) and high specificity (73% to 84%) among women younger than 65 (Carolyn J Crandall, 2015; Pecina, Romanovsky, Merry, Kennel, & Thacher, 2016) (see Appendix A, Table 1). Cheung and colleagues (2013) evaluated possible FRAX-based intervention among Chinese postmenopausal women in Hong Kong and found that the FRAX threshold of 9.95% had sensitivity and specificity of 62% and 73%, respectively (Cheung, Cheung, Kung, & Tan, 2014). High specificity of FRAX indicated that the prescreening

tool is useful in reducing the number of women at low risk being sent for unnecessary DEXA scan.

Determinants of Osteoporosis Prescreening

Provider Factors

Despite evidence supporting the guidelines, providers often fail to recognize individuals at risk for (Office of the Surgeon General (US), 2004). As discussed earlier, two studies found that DEXA was significantly underutilized in women who were at high risk for osteoporosis (Brennan, Wactawski-Wende, Crespo, & Dmochowski, 2004; Hamrick et al., 2012). On the other hand, overuse of DEXA screening was reported among younger postmenopausal women who were not eligible for such screening (Amarnath et al., 2015; Schnatz et al., 2011). Some common provider determinants of screening inconsistency include HCP uncertainty of the effectiveness of recommended guidelines, unawareness of osteoporosis prevalence, and concern about cost (Smita Nayak et al., 2009; Papa & Weber, 1997) (see Appendix A, Table 2).

Additional provider factors were provider gender, subspecialty, practice site, and larger patient volumes. For instance, sites with optimal osteoporosis screening rates specialize in women's health (Teng, Curtis, & Saag, 2009). A systematic review (Morris et al., 2004) demonstrated that female providers, bone disease specialists, and those caring for more women were positively correlated with utilizing guidelines for BMD screenings. In contrast, evidence found that physician gender, age, and status were not affiliated with rates of osteoporosis screening (Grover et al., 2009).

Patient Factors and Perceptions

Several patient factors and attitudes have been linked to osteoporosis screening behaviors. Increased age (65 years and older) or higher height placed women at greater risk for inadequate access to osteoporosis screening (Smita Nayak et al., 2009). Another study showed that those women who have not completed a preventative health examination during recent years were under-screened for osteoporosis (Grover et al., 2009). Only 20% of postmenopausal women showed acceptable knowledge of osteoporosis disease (Palacios et al., 2009). Two qualitative studies (Sale et al., 2014; Sale et al., 2016) found that patient barriers to the understanding of the concepts of osteoporosis included misconceptions about risk factors, lack of follow-up with providers after a fracture, and HCP miscommunication about risk status.

Conclusions from Literature Review

Evidence from the literature review shows that the use of prescreening tools for identification of osteoporosis and prediction of fracture in postmenopausal women is imperative. Existing risk assessment instruments are accessible and inexpensive. The primary cost is the time it takes to perform the assessment (Smita Nayak et al., 2011). There is controversy regarding the best instrument to measure the risks of fractures or osteoporosis. Previous studies have not focused on the use of osteoporosis prescreening screening tools in Vietnamese American samples. For this project, OSTA and FRAX instruments, identified as an innovation construct, are representative of validated risk assessment tools that can identify the need for BMD screening in postmenopausal Vietnamese American women ages 45 to 64 at the clinic.

METHODS

Ethical Issues

Several ethical considerations were taken into account before conducting this project. A letter for permission for use of data was obtained from the clinic administrator (see Appendix E). Prior to data collection, the project was submitted to the Institutional Review Board of California State University at Fullerton (CSUF) for review to ensure that ethical standards were being followed. The review board authorized that the project could be done with a waiver of patient's consent. The author who is the employee of the clinic collected and evaluated the data, put the complete data set into a data file with no patient identifiers (no link to medical record number). This file was shared with the Chair of this doctoral project.

Setting

This retrospective chart review aimed to compare the differences in positive osteoporosis screens (according to DEXA) for the OSTA and FRAX tools. The project took place at a multi-practitioner primary care setting in Southern California. Eight medical doctors, three physician assistants, and two nurse practitioners serve as the primary care providers for patients age 18 and over. Patients come to the clinic for various medical conditions. The majority of clinic patients are Vietnamese who were born in the U.S. or immigrants from Viet Nam.

Sample

Inclusion criteria included Vietnamese women who were postmenopausal, aged 45 to 64, and had results in the EHR from a DEXA test performed within a two-year period. Exclusion criteria included females with secondary osteoporosis or history of metabolic

bone disease (e.g., type 1 diabetes, hypoparathyroidism, Paget's disease, osteogenesis imperfecta), renal impairment, organ transplantation, and any life-threatening condition. Postmenopausal woman was defined as having had no menstrual periods for at least 12 consecutive months.

Procedures

A retrospective chart review was performed to determine the number of women who had a DEXA test performed within the 2-year period. EHR review was done from April 1, 2017 and continued for six months until October 2, 2017.

To obtain the sample, all women 45 to 64 who had at least one encounter in the project setting between April 1 and October 2, 2017 were identified (see Figure 2 for flowchart of sample accrual). The index date was taken as the date of the most recent encounter in women who had more than one encounter during the sampling window. A list of women and medical record numbers was generated to allow the author to collect data needed. Of 149 qualified women, 141 women had BMD at both femoral neck and lumbar spine sites; three women had BMD at femoral neck (FN) only, and eight women had BMD at lumbar spine (LS) only. According to WHO, the reference standard for diagnosing osteoporosis is BMD at femoral neck; however, other central body sites such as total hips and lumbar spines can be used for diagnosis in clinical settings (World Health Organization, 2004a).

Figure 2. Electronic Health Record review flowchart.

Data Collection

A data collection tool was developed. Physical measurements consisted of height, weight, and DEXA scan *t*-score within the past two years. Height and weight were used

to calculate body mass index (BMI). The EHR calculates BMI automatically once weight and height are entered into the system. If BMI was not available, it was calculated by dividing the weight (kg) by the square of the height (m). When patients undergo DEXA scans, the BMD *t*-scores are often available in the EHR database. If a patient record showed that a DEXA scan was ordered or completed but the BMD results were not available, a follow up phone call to one of the radiology centers was made to obtain BMD results.

Demographic and health history data collected were as follows: age, cigarette smoking (yes/no), alcohol intake (yes/no), previous fractures (yes/no), history of a parent with fractured hip (yes/no), prolonged use of glucocorticoid for over three months (yes/no), history of rheumatoid arthritis (yes/no), and presence of at least one secondary osteoporosis factor (yes = presence of hyperthyroidism, hypogonadism, chronic liver disease, or chronic malnutrition). This data was used to calculate risk scores for the OSTA and FRAX tools (see Appendix C for description of risk factors and scoring). If information was missing or incomplete in the database, women were excluded. For diagnoses of rheumatoid arthritis and conditions related to secondary osteoporosis (e.g., hyperthyroidism, hypogonadism, chronic liver disease, and chronic malnutrition), problem lists were used to identify relevant ICD -10 (International Classification of Disease-10) diagnosis codes. Medication list and e-prescriptions were used to identify whether patients had been given enough glucocorticoids treatment to meet FRAX risk factor definition. Other risk factors were obtained from medical, social, and family histories. The office staff and providers were encouraged to update health history and diagnoses during office visits.

Risk Assessment Tools

Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asians (OSTA)

The OSTA score is calculated by subtracting the patient's age from body weight and multiplying by 0.2. The formula follows:

$$[\text{Body weight (kg)} - \text{Age (year)}] \times 0.2$$

The OSTA score was rounded to the nearest whole number. Age was automatically calculated when the patient's date of birth by day, month and year was entered into the EHR system. Age was rounded to the whole year. At the clinic, weight was measured with the subject wearing light indoor clothing and no shoes; the same digital scale was used for all patients. The subjects with the cut-off threshold OSTA score of ≤ -1.0 were classified as having high risk for osteoporosis, and those with the values > -1.0 were considered as a moderate or low risk.

Fracture Risk Assessment Tool (FRAX)

The FRAX score was determined by using a computer-based algorithm at the following website: <https://www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/tool.jsp>. Clinical risk factors required to calculate FRAX scores are age, sex, weight, height, cigarette smoking, alcohol use, previous fractures, parent fractured hip, glucocorticoid use, rheumatoid arthritis, secondary osteoporosis, and femoral neck BMD *t*-scores. The FRAX tool calculates the 10-year probability of suffering a MOF, as well as the 10-year probability of suffering a hip fracture. The USPSTF recommends the FRAX cut-off threshold score for a major osteoporosis fracture (MOF) of $\geq 9.3\%$ as indicative of requiring osteoporosis screening. This project focused on the usefulness of the FRAX tool for predicting osteoporosis; therefore, a 10-year fracture probability was obtained, but did not include a BMD

measurement. When using the FRAX tool, in addition to the clinical risk factors, the score was calibrated for persons in certain geographic regions and ethnicities, including U.S.-Asia and Asia-China. As a calibration for Viet Nam was not available, the calculation tool for Asia-China was used for this project when scoring Vietnamese patients due to the geographic and cultural closeness between China and Viet Nam. The U.S.-Asian calculations were not selected because most of the patients at this primary care clinic grew up and spent their peak bone mass building years in Viet Nam prior to settlement in the U.S. Therefore, the U.S.-Asian calculation would not capture the changes in bone mass experience by immigrant Vietnamese patients.

Bone Mass Density Measurement

The BMD was measured at L1-L4 lumbar spine and femoral neck using DEXA scan. Most patients underwent BMD testing by DEXA at either an in-house radiology center or nearby medical imaging center. The machines used at both centers were GE Lunar Podigy Advance (nearby imaging center) and GE Lunar PDX (in house). BMD results, recorded as absolute values in grams per square centimeter, are expressed as *t*-scores. Using the WHO classification, osteoporosis is defined as a *t*-score of 2.5 standard deviations (*SD*) or more below the young female adult mean. Osteopenia is a *t*-score of femoral neck with *SD*s between -1.0 and -2.5 (World Health Organization, 2004a) (see Table 2). All NHANES III *t*-score measurements were standardized using Hologic densitometer (Wu, 2012). There were controversial issues regarding the use of GE Lunar and Hologic densitometers. Therefore, in 2002, the International Society for Clinical Densitometry recommended the use of the lowest *t*-score at the FN instead of trochanter *t*-

score for the diagnosis of osteoporosis when using GE Lunar machines (Binkley et al., 2005).

Data Analysis

This project aimed to retrospectively compare the sensitivity and specificity of the OSTA and FRAX in identifying Vietnamese women, ages 45 to 64 years, who received a DEXA scan for osteoporosis screening. Sensitivity and specificity of a clinical test (DEXA) were used to quantify the diagnostic accuracy of two prescreening instruments (Altman & Bland, 1994). Sensitivity predicts that if the individual has the condition, the test will be positive. On contrary, specificity indicates that if the individual does not have the condition, the test will be negative (Lalkhen & McCluskey, 2008).

Additionally, this project evaluated how many patients received a DEXA scan with negative findings for osteoporosis (meaning they may have undergone unnecessary DEXA). For OSTA scores, the cut-off value for OSTA is -1; therefore, women with values of -1 or less are considered at high risk for osteoporosis and thus, are recommended for DEXA screening. A value > 0 indicates low risk, and moderate risk ranges from $-1 < \text{OSTA score} \leq 0$. The FRAX scores without BMD values were estimated by manually entering each clinical risk factor in the calculation tool for Asia-China via the computer-based algorithm (www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/tool). Women with 9.3% or greater risk of 10-year MOF probability, or 3% or greater risk of 10-year hip fracture probability, are candidates for DEXA screening. The categories of the osteoporosis risk index for each tool were confirmed by the appropriate OSTA and FRAX assessment threshold chart (See Appendix B & C).

Using 2004 WHO criteria, women with BMD measurements were categorized as positive DEXA (t -score ≤ -2.5) for osteoporosis or negative DEXA (t -score > -2.5) for non-osteoporosis (osteopenia or normal). Sensitivity was defined as the proportion of women with osteoporosis who tested positive (OSTA < -1 ; FRAX $\geq 9.3\%$ for MOF risk or $\geq 3\%$ for hip fractures). Specificity was determined as the proportion of women without osteoporosis who tested normal (OSTA > -1 ; FRAX $< 9.3\%$ for MOF or $< 3\%$ for hip fractures).

To examine the prevalence of osteoporosis across various groups of women of different ages, women were categorized based on age: Category 1 was women 45-50 years of age (when women are at low risk and screening is uncommonly recommended); Category 2 consisted of women 51-59 years of age (when most women are in age of menopause); and Category 3 was women age 60-64 (when women are at higher risk and screening may often be indicated).

RESULTS

Sample Demographics

An EHR review identified 2229 women ages between 45 to 64 years who had at least one office encounter at the primary care setting from April 1 to October 2, 2017. Of these women, 2080 were excluded due to having no DEXA screening, bone scan at sites other than hips and lumbar spine, missing BMD result or risk factors, or DEXA screening more than two years at the time of the office encounter, resulting in a sample of 149 (6.9%) participants (see Figure 2). Description of the distribution of these participants for risk factors, BMD results, and absolute 10-year fracture risk are shown in Table 4. Women's average age was 59.28 ± 3.87 years-old; their mean weight, height and BMI were 119.45 ± 17.59 lbs., 59.88 ± 2.12 cm, and 23.30 ± 3.11 kg/m², respectively. The mean OSTA score for the entire sample was -1.02. Correspondingly, the mean 10-year predicted major osteoporotic fracture risk by FRAX without BMD was 3.59, and the mean 10-year predicted hip fracture risk by FRAX without BMD was 0.63. Among the 149 women, three (2%) women did not receive DEXA at FN, and eight (5.4%) women did not receive DEXA at LS. As the result, the mean *t*-score of the FN was -1.99, and the mean *t*-score of LS was -2.12. Of all women, fewer than 1% (0.7%) had greater than one risk factor for osteoporosis other than weight/height (e.g., BMI) and age.

Prediction of Osteoporosis by OSTA

The results for the prediction of osteoporosis using OSTA are summarized in Tables 5 and 6. For the FN results, the OSTA identified 32 of 48 women with osteoporosis, excluding 16 of 98 women without osteoporosis, resulting in sensitivity and specificity of 66.7% and 16.3%, respectively. For LS, the OSTA identified 37 of 60

women with osteoporosis, excluding 24 of 81 women without osteoporosis, resulting in sensitivity and specificity of 61.7% and 29.6%.

Table 4

Selected baseline demographics of 149 study participants

Characteristics	Mean (SD) Range	N (%)
Weight (pounds)	119.45 (17.59)	
Height (inches)	59.88 (2.12)	
BMI (pounds/inches ²)	23.30 (3.11)	
Age	59.28 (3.87) 49 to 65 ^a	
Previous Fracture - no		149 (100)
Parental hip fracture – no		149 (100)
Current smoker - no		149 (100)
Steroid user > 3 months - no		149 (100)
Rheumatoid arthritis – no		148 (99.3)
Secondary osteoporosis - no		149 (100)
Alcohol > 3 drinks/day - no		149 (100)
^bRisk factors combined- no		148 (99.3)
Femoral neck <i>t</i> -score result (not used in calculating FRAX score)	-1.99 (.79) -3.90-.65	141
Lumbar spine <i>t</i> -score result	-2.12 (1.28) -5.10-4.00	146
OSTA score	-1.02 (1.70) -5.09 – 4.57	
10-year fracture risk FRAX:	3.59 (1.60)	
MOF without using BMD	.50-8.00	
Hip fracture without using BMD	.63 (.33) .10-1.80	

Note. N = 149. BMI = bone mineral density; DEXA = dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; FRAX = fracture risk assessment tool; MOF = major osteoporotic fracture; OSTA = osteoporosis self-assessment in Asians
^a65 year old had DEXA scan before 65th birthday

^b Combined risk factors: one or more of the following: previous fracture, parental hip fracture, current smoke, steroid use > 3 months, rheumatoid arthritis, secondary osteoporosis, or alcohol use

Age alone was the most significant risk factor of osteoporosis for these postmenopausal women when using OSTA. For women aged 51 to 59 years, under the OSTA strategy, only 37% of women with t -score ≤ -2.5 would be referred for BMD testing, compared with 79% for women aged 60 to 64 years with t -score ≤ -2.5 . The prevalence of osteoporosis was very high in postmenopausal women in this age category. For younger postmenopausal women, the OSTA identified 100% women aged 45 to 50 years as being at risk for osteoporosis, however, this data may not represent a relevant result due to a very small sample size ($n = 3$) (Table 7).

Table 5

Osteoporosis Screening of OSTA Compared to the DEXA Scan of the Lumbar Spine (#/% of women distributed in each category) N = 141

BMD	Positive OSTA (≤ -1.0)	Negative OSTA (moderate risk) ($-1 < \text{OSTA} \leq 0$)	Negative OSTA (low risk) (> 0)	Total
DEXA +	37 true (61.7)	10 (16.7)	13 (21.7)	60
DEXA -	42 (51.9)	15 true (18.5)	24 true (29.6)	81
Total	79	25	37	141

Note. BMD = Bone Mass Density; DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; OSTA = Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asians

Sensitivity = true positive/true positive + false negative = $37/79 = .47$ or 47%

Specificity = true negative/true negative + false positive = $(15+24)/(15+24)+42=39/81=.48$ or 48%

Positive predictive value = true positive/true positive + false positive = $37/37+23=.61$ or 61%

Negative predictive value = true negative/true negative + false negative = $39/25+38=.63$ or 63%

Table 6

Osteoporosis Screening of OSTA Compared to the DEXA Scan of the Femur (#/% of women distributed in each category) N =146

BMD	Positive OSTA (≤ -1.0)	Negative OSTA (moderate risk) ($-1 < \text{OSTA} \leq 0$)	Negative OSTA (low risk) (> 0)	Total
DEXA +	32 true (66.7)	10 (20.8)	6 (12.5)	48
DEXA -	50 (51.0)	16 true (16.3)	32 true (32.7)	98
Total	82	26	38	146

Note. BMD = Bone Mass Density; DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; OSTA = Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asians

Sensitivity = true positive/true positive + false negative = $32/32+(10+6) = .67$ or 67%

Specificity = true negative/true negative + false positive = $(16+32)/(16+32) + 50=48/98 = .49$ or 49%

Positive predictive value = true positive/true positive + false positive = $32/32+50=.39$ or 39%

Negative predictive value = true negative/true negative + false negative = $48/48+16=48/64=.75$ or 75%

Prediction of Osteoporosis by FRAX

Table 8 and 9 were used to summarize the performance of FRAX tool for primary osteoporosis in postmenopausal Vietnamese women living in U.S. For both the FN and LS, FRAX did not identify any women with osteoporosis and excluded all women without osteoporosis, resulting in corresponding sensitivity and specificity of 0% and 100%.

Table 7

Prevalence of Osteoporosis (Positive DEXA) by Age (Number [%] of Women per Category) N=149

Age	DEXA (T score \leq -2.5) (femoral neck or lumbar spine)	OSTA (\leq -1)	FRAX (\geq 9.3%)	FRAX (\geq 3.51%)
45-50 (n = 3)	1/3 (33)	1/1 (100)	0/1	0/1
51-59 (n = 62)	31/62 (50)	13/31 (42)	0/30	6/31 (19)
60-64 (n = 84)	45/84 (54)	35/45 (78)	0/47	22/45 (49)

Note. DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; FRAX = Fracture risk assessment tool; OSTA = Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asians

Prevalence of Osteoporosis by Age

In this sample of Vietnamese born postmenopausal women, prevalence of osteoporosis did not differ for the two older age groups: 51-59 vs. 60-64, $\chi^2(2) = .595$, $p = .743$ (Table 6). Of women screened with DEXA (femoral or lumbar), about half of women 60-64 (54%) and 51-59 (50%) were found likely to have osteoporosis (t -score \leq -2.5), compared to one-third in the 45-50 age group. The OSTA and FRAX prescreens (both levels) were more accurate among women in the oldest age group and each found increasing numbers of women to be at risk as age increased. For example, OSTA prescreening would have found 42% of women 51-59 to need DEXA contrasting with 78% of women 60-64; similarly, FRAX ($>$ 3.51%) would have found 22 (49%) women in the oldest group contrasting with 6 (19%) of women in the middle age group. It is hard to interpret the data related to the youngest age group due to the small number of women ages 40-49.

Table 8

Osteoporosis Screening of FRAX Compared to the DEXA Scan of the Lumbar Spine (#/% of Women Distributed in Each Category) N =141

Bone mineral density	Positive FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$)	Negative FRAX	Total
DEXA +		60 (100)	60
DEXA -		81 true (100)	81
Total	0	141	141

Note. DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; FRAX = Fracture risk assessment tool

Sensitivity = true positive/true positive + false negative = 0

Specificity = true negative/true negative + false positive = 1.0

Positive predictive value = true positive/true positive + false positive = 0

Negative predictive value = true negative/true negative + false negative = 1.0

Table 9

Osteoporosis Screening of FRAX Compared to the DEXA Scan of the Femur (#/% of Women Distributed in Each Category) N =146

Bone mineral density	Positive FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$)	Negative FRAX	Total
DEXA +		48 (100)	48
DEXA -		98 true (100)	98
Total	0	146	146

Note. DEXA = Dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry; FRAX = Fracture risk assessment tool

Sensitivity = true positive/true positive + false negative = 0

Specificity = true negative/true negative + false positive = $98/98+48 = .67$ or 67%

Positive predictive value = true positive/true positive + false positive = 0

Negative predictive value = true negative/true negative + false negative = $98/98+0= 1.0$

DISCUSSION

This project examined the ability of OSTA and FRAX (without BMD) in identifying osteoporosis among Vietnamese American postmenopausal women aged 45 to 64 years. These tools were applied to women who had received BMD testing for osteoporosis prior to the study. There were clinically significant differences for OSTA and FRAX in identifying osteoporosis. The OSTA, based on body weight and age, had higher sensitivity and lower specificity compared to FRAX, which means that OSTA was more helpful in screening for osteoporosis, and thus, higher risk of fractures with falls. The high sensitivity (66.7%) of OSTA shown indicates that as a prescreening tool, it identifies Vietnamese American women who are at risk for osteoporosis much better than FRAX (which identified none). Use of the OSTA would help providers know which women need further BMD testing, which may lead to a reduction in missed diagnoses. The OSTA performed slightly better at the femoral site to identify BMD loss than at the lumbar spine. Moreover, the performance of OSTA for the 60-64 age group was superior to that of the younger age groups. This means, for OSTA, advanced age was a strong predictor for increased risk for osteoporosis in the project sample.

Conversely, FRAX scores (threshold $\geq 9.3\%$) showed all women as having no risk for osteoporosis, with specificity of 100%. This means that as a result of the no risk findings of the FRAX, Vietnamese American women prescreened with FRAX would not undergo DEXA testing if this USPTSF-recommended tool were used. However, since FRAX did not detect women who did have osteoporosis, it had no predictive value, with sensitivity of 0%. Moreover, for FRAX, when other risk factors were not present, age alone was not positively associated with increased rate of osteoporosis. The missed

diagnosis of osteoporosis is worrisome because these postmenopausal women may be appropriate candidates for treatment.

These findings are consistent with prior studies. Jiang et al. (2016) reported that FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$) was not sufficient for identifying women at risk for osteoporosis compared to OSTA and other tools for osteoporosis identification among postmenopausal women. Similarly, in a cohort of women ages 50 to 64, Crandall et al. (2014) found that FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$) was inferior to OSTA in identifying women with osteoporosis. These authors recommended that an alternative cut-off threshold ($\geq 3.51\%$) for FRAX be used to provide acceptable sensitivity of 95%. This would improve the detection of osteoporosis by using a t -scores ≤ -2.5 . In the current project, Vietnamese women aged 45 to 64 years, using the proposed FRAX cutoff of $\geq 3.51\%$, 28 (36%) women had a t -score ≤ -2.5 and would be referred for BMD testing. This is compared to no women (0%) identified when using the FRAX ($\geq 9.3\%$), and 49 (63%) women using the OSTA. This indicates that when FRAX threshold is lowered, it increases the likelihood that potential osteoporosis will be detected.

The present project has significant clinical value. A comprehensive literature review showed that no prior studies compared FRAX to OSTA among Vietnamese postmenopausal women aged 45 to 64. Even with the FRAX scores adjusted for by country, its threshold lowered to $\geq 3.51\%$ to increase sensitivity, the number of women with positive osteoporosis sent for DEXA suggests that the OSTA is superior to FRAX in detecting osteoporosis among Vietnamese postmenopausal women.

The project has several strengths. First, the study sample was homogeneous in age, ethnicity and medical history. Second, the study followed strict inclusion and exclusion

criteria to reduce the possibility of extraneous variables. Third, the sample size was considered adequate. These strengths help to increase the validity of the project.

Limitations

The project had some limitations. First this was a retrospective chart review. Therefore, data collection solely relied on medical records which might have incomplete risk factor information. For instance, the risk factors such as use of corticosteroid, secondary osteoporosis, and parental hip fracture were sometimes not captured in the EHR. Possible reasons for missing information could be inconsistency of documentation and patients' unreliable history of past medical conditions, leading to missing valid risk factors in the EHR. It is also worth noting that the prevalence for these risk factors in this project was lower than that observed in other samples. This low prevalence could have been the result of the underestimates of the FRAX scores. Hence, given the low number of screening-eligible women when applying EHR data to the FRAX algorithm.

Second, the women's weight and height were not taken at the same time as the BMD were measured. This could result in an inaccurate interpretation of both OSTA and FRAX scores. Third, the project included only individuals who attended at least one office visit during the project period and did not include those who had no follow-up appointments, missed visits, and lack of documentation. Therefore, the sample may not represent other populations in the service setting. Finally, data was collected at a single small primary care setting in Southern California, and therefore findings cannot be generalized to all Vietnamese American women.

Implications for Next Steps

This project aimed to identify a validated screening instrument that can be used for Vietnamese American women in a busy primary care setting. The implications for the future are indicated below:

- 1) The author will continue data collection for 12 - 24 months to capture more women who might not have a chance to attend an office visit during the project period. Majority of healthy working-age postmenopausal patients are much less likely to visit their doctors within a year. According to the 2015 National Health Interview Survey, among adults aged 45 to 64, one in eight had not visited their doctor for more than six months to a year (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017).
- 2) This is a retrospective chart review; therefore, a structured patient questionnaire regarding demographics and clinical risk factors for osteoporosis are recommended during office visits in order to obtain more accurate and consistent patient data.
- 3) The author will share results of the project with HCP colleagues and clinic staff to increase their awareness, attitudes and acceptance regarding the use of prescreening tools for osteoporosis within the project setting.
- 4) As a facilitator, the author will seek the support and guidance of management for implementing prescreening tools for osteoporosis. This could promote consistency in the use of the instrument across HCPs. This will more likely identify women with osteoporosis risk factors (and thus, needing DEXA scans) than the current practice. This becomes important since according the Centers

for Medicare and Medicaid Services, Medicare will only reimburse for DEXA scan on eligible patients (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, 2007).

Conclusions

Neither OSTA nor FRAX effectively predicted all DEXA scan results, and therefore, could not accurately predict the fracture risks for osteoporosis for all postmenopausal Vietnamese American women ages 45 to 64 in the project setting. However, OSTA, a simple easy to use tool based on BMI and age, has superior predictive value over FRAX to detect fracture risk among older postmenopausal women. This could be a major advantage to providers when choosing prescreening options. In addition, the OSTA, a well-known tool, has been validated for osteoporosis prescreening in other populations. Moreover, the OSTA is available and assessible as a free online calculation tool. Thus, this makes it easy to use in the clinical practice. Future projects are recommended to identify effective prescreening tools for osteoporosis among postmenopausal Vietnamese American women in other practice settings.

REFERENCES

- Ahmadzadeh, A., Emam, M., Rajaei, A., Moslemizadeh, M., & Jalessi, M. (2014). Comparison of three different osteoporosis risk assessment tools: ORAI (osteoporosis risk assessment instrument), SCORE (simple calculated osteoporosis risk estimation) and OST (osteoporosis self-assessment tool). *Medical Journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*.
- Altman, D. G., & Bland, J. M. (1994). Diagnostic tests. 1: Sensitivity and specificity. *BMJ: British Medical Journal*, 308(6943), 1552.
- Amarnath, A. L. D., Franks, P., Robbins, J. A., Xing, G., & Fenton, J. J. (2015). Underuse and overuse of osteoporosis screening in a regional health system: A retrospective cohort study. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 30(12), 1733-1740.
- American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons. (2014). Surgery to repair a hip fracture reduces lifetime health care costs by more than \$65,000 per patient, adds years of patient life quality and mobility. Retrieved from <http://newsroom.aaos.org/media-resources/Press-releases/surgery-to-repair-a-hip-fracture-reduces-lifetime-health-care-costs-by-more-than-65000-per-patient-adds-years-of-patient-life-quality-and-mobility.htm>
- American College of Physicians. (2016). Trends in potential overuse of three services among individuals with employer sponsored health Insurance. Retrieved from https://www.ahip.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/TrendsinOveruse_Report_3-21-16.pdf
- Andreoli, T. E., Carpenter, C. C. J., Griggs, R. C., & Benjamin, I. J. (2007). *Andreoli and Carpenter's Cecil essentials of medicine*. St. Louis, MO: Saunders Elsevier.

- Bansal, S., Pecina, J., Merry, S., Kennel, K., Maxson, J., Quigg, S., & Thacher, T. (2015). US Preventative Services Task Force FRAX threshold has a low sensitivity to detect osteoporosis in women ages 50–64 years. *Osteoporosis International*, *26*(4), 1429-1433.
- Barrett-Connor, E., Siris, E. S., Wehren, L. E., Miller, P. D., Abbott, T. A., Berger, M. L., . . . Sherwood, L. M. (2005). Osteoporosis and Fracture Risk in Women of Different Ethnic Groups. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, *20*(2), 185-194. doi:10.1359/JBMR.041007
- Binkley, N., Kiebzak, G. M., Lewiecki, E. M., Krueger, D., Gangnon, R. E., Miller, P. D., . . . Drezner, M. K. (2005). Recalculation of the NHANES database SD improves T-Score agreement and reduces osteoporosis prevalence. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, *20*(2), 195-201.
- Boskey, A. L., DiCarlo, E., Paschalis, E., West, P., & Mendelsohn, R. (2005). Comparison of mineral quality and quantity in iliac crest biopsies from high- and low-turnover osteoporosis: An FT-IR microspectroscopic investigation. *Osteoporosis International*, *16*(12), 2031-2038. doi:10.1007/s00198-005-1992-3
- Brennan, R. M., Wactawski-Wende, J., Crespo, C. J., & Dmochowski, J. (2004). Factors associated with treatment initiation after osteoporosis screening. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, *160*(5), 475-483.
- Brown, D., & McCormack, B. (2005). Developing postoperative pain management: Utilising the promoting action on research implementation in health services (PARIHS) framework. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, *2*(3), 131-141.

- Buehring, B., Viswanathan, R., Binkley, N., & Busse, W. (2013). Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis: An update on effects and management. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, *132*(5), 1019-1030.
doi:<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2013.08.040>
- Buttaro, T. M., Trybulski, J., Bailey, P., & Sandberg-Cook, J. (Eds.). (2007). *Primary care: A collaborative practice* (3rd ed.): St. Louis, MO: Mosby/Elsevier.
- Cauley, J. A. (2011). Defining ethnic and racial differences in osteoporosis and fragility fractures. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, *469*(7), 1891-1899.
doi:10.1007/s11999-011-1863-5
- Cavalier, E., Bergmann, P., Bruyère, O., Delanaye, P., Durnez, A., Devogelaer, J.-P., . . . Kaufman, J.-M. (2016). The role of biochemical of bone turnover markers in osteoporosis and metabolic bone disease: A consensus paper of the Belgian Bone Club. *Osteoporosis International*, *27*(7), 2181-2195.
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention. (2015). Osteoporosis or low bone mass at the femur neck or lumbar spine in older adults: United States, 2005–2008. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/databriefs/db93.htm>
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention. (2016). Hip fracture among older adults. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/homeandrecreationalafety/falls/adulthipfx.html>
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention. (2017). Ambulatory care use and physician office visits. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/fastats/physician-visits.htm>

- Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services. (2007). CMS Manual System: Bone mass measurement. Retrieved from <https://www.cms.gov/Regulations-and-Guidance/Guidance/Transmittals/Downloads/R70BP.pdf>
- Centre for Metabolic Bone Diseases. (n.d.). FRAX Fracture risk assessment tool. Retrieved from <https://www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/index.aspx>
- Chen, S.-J., Chen, Y.-J., Cheng, C.-H., Hwang, H.-F., Chen, C.-Y., & Lin, M.-R. (2016). Comparisons of Different Screening Tools for Identifying Fracture/Osteoporosis Risk Among Community-Dwelling Older People. *Medicine*, *95*(20), e3415. doi:10.1097/MD.00000000000003415
- Cheung, E., Cheung, C.-L., Kung, A. W. C., & Tan, K. C. B. (2014). Possible FRAX-based intervention thresholds for a cohort of Chinese postmenopausal women. *Osteoporosis International*, *25*(3), 1017-1023. doi:10.1007/s00198-013-2553-9
- Christensen, L., Iqbal, S., Macarios, D., Badamgarav, E., & Harley, C. (2010). Cost of fractures commonly associated with osteoporosis in a managed-care population. *Journal of Medical Economics*, *13*(2), 302-313.
- Crandall, C. J. (2015). Risk assessment tools for osteoporosis screening in postmenopausal women: A systematic review. *Current Osteoporosis Reports*, *13*(5), 287-301.
- Crandall, C. J., Larson, J., Gourlay, M. L., Donaldson, M. G., LaCroix, A., Cauley, J. A., . . . Ensrud, K. E. (2014). Osteoporosis Screening in Postmenopausal Women 50 to 64 Years Old: Comparison of US Preventive Services Task Force strategy and two traditional strategies in the Women's Health Initiative. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, *29*(7), 1661-1666. doi:10.1002/jbmr.2174

- Dawson-Hughes, B., Heaney, R. P., Holick, M. F., Lips, P., Meunier, P. J., & Vieth, R. (2005). Estimates of optimal vitamin D status. *Osteoporosis International*, *16*(7), 713-716.
- Delmas, P., Eastell, R., Garnero, P., Seibel, M., & Stepan, J. (2000). The use of biochemical markers of bone turnover in osteoporosis. *Osteoporosis International*, *11*(6), S2-S17.
- Edwards, F. D., Grover, M. L., Cook, C. B., & Chang, Y.-H. H. (2014). Use of FRAX as a determinant for risk-based osteoporosis screening may decrease unnecessary testing while improving the odds of identifying treatment candidates. *Women's Health Issues*, *24*(6), 629-634.
- Gourlay, M. L., Miller, W. C., Richey, F., Garrett, J. M., Hanson, L. C., & Reginster, J.-Y. (2005). Performance of osteoporosis risk assessment tools in postmenopausal women aged 45–64 years. *Osteoporosis International*, *16*(8), 921-927.
- Grover, M., Anderson, M., Gupta, R., Haden, M., Hartmark-Hill, J., Morski, L. M., . . . Dueck, A. (2009). Increased osteoporosis screening rates associated with the provision of a preventive health examination. *The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine*, *22*(6), 655-662.
- Hamrick, I., Cao, Q., Agbafé-Mosley, D., & Cummings, D. M. (2012). Osteoporosis healthcare disparities in postmenopausal women. *Journal of Women's Health*, *21*(12), 1232-1236.
- Harvey, G., & Kitson, A. (2016). PARIHS revisited: from heuristic to integrated framework for the successful implementation of knowledge into practice. *Implementation Science*, *11*(1), 1-33. doi:10.1186/s13012-016-0398-2

- Henneicke, H., Gasparini, S. J., Brennan-Speranza, T. C., Zhou, H., & Seibel, M. J. (2014). Glucocorticoids and bone: Local effects and systemic implications. *Trends in Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 25(4), 197-211.
doi:<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.tem.2013.12.006>
- Hoeffel, E., Rastogi, S., Kim, M. O., & Shahid, H. (2012). The Asian Population: 2000. Retrieved from <https://www.census.gov/prod/cen2010/briefs/c2010br-11.pdf>
- Holick, M. F., Binkley, N. C., Bischoff-Ferrari, H. A., Gordon, C. M., Hanley, D. A., Heaney, R. P., . . . Weaver, C. M. (2011). Evaluation, treatment, and prevention of vitamin D deficiency: An Endocrine society clinical practice guideline. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 96(7), 1911-1930.
- International Osteoporosis Foundation. (2008). Clinician's guide to prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. Retrieved from http://osteoporosis.utorontoeit.com/PDFs/NOF_Clinicians_Guide.pdf
- International Osteoporosis Foundation. (2009). Facts and statistics about osteoporosis and its impact. Retrieved from <http://www.iofbonehealth.org/facts-and-statistics.html>
- International Osteoporosis Foundation. (2015a). Fracture risk assessment. Retrieved from <https://www.iofbonehealth.org/osteoporosis-musculoskeletal-disorders/osteoporosis/diagnosis/fracture-risk-assessment>
- International Osteoporosis Foundation. (2015b). Vitamin D. Retrieved from <https://www.iofbonehealth.org/osteoporosis-musculoskeletal-disorders/osteoporosis/prevention/vitamin-d>

- Jiang, X., Good, L. E., Spinka, R., & Schnatz, P. F. (2016). Osteoporosis screening in postmenopausal women aged 50–64 years: BMI alone compared with current screening tools. *Maturitas*, *83*, 59-64.
- Kaczkowski, C., & Frey, R. J. (2013). Osteoporosis. In B. Narins (Ed.), *The Gale encyclopedia of nursing and allied health* (3rd ed., vol. 4, pp. 2456-2463). Detroit: Gale.
- Kanis, J., Odén, A., Johnell, O., Johansson, H., De Laet, C., Brown, J., . . . Cummings, S. (2007). The use of clinical risk factors enhances the performance of BMD in the prediction of hip and osteoporotic fractures in men and women. *Osteoporosis International*, *18*(8), 1033-1046.
- Kanis, J. A., McCloskey, E. V., Johansson, H., Oden, A., Melton Iii, L. J., & Khaltsev, N. (2008). A reference standard for the description of osteoporosis. *Bone*, *42*(3), 467-475. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bone.2007.11.001>
- Kitson, A., Harvey, G., & McCormack, B. (1998). Enabling the implementation of evidence based practice: A conceptual framework. *Quality in Health Care*, *7*(3), 149-158. doi:[10.1136/qshc.7.3.149](http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/qshc.7.3.149)
- Koh, L., Ben Sedrine, W., Torralba, T., Kung, A., Fujiwara, S., Chan, S., . . . Park, H. (2001). A simple tool to identify Asian women at increased risk of osteoporosis. *Osteoporosis International*, *12*(8), 699-705.
- Lalkhen, A. G., & McCluskey, A. (2008). Clinical tests: Sensitivity and specificity. *Continuing Education in Anaesthesia, Critical Care & Pain*, *8*(6), 221-223.

- Lauderdale, D. S., Kuohung, V., Chang, S.-L., & Chin, M. H. (2003). Identifying older chinese immigrants at high risk for osteoporosis. *Journal of General Internal Medicine, 18*(7), 508-515. doi:10.1046/j.1525-1497.2003.20331.x
- Lu, C., Chen, D., Cai, Y., & Wei, S. (2006). Concordance of OSTA and lumbar spine BMD by DXA in identifying risk of osteoporosis. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery and Research, 1*, 1-14. doi:10.1186/1749-799X
- Masi, L. (2008). Epidemiology of osteoporosis. *Clinical Cases in Mineral and Bone Metabolism, 5*(1), 11-13.
- McLendon, A. N., & Woodis, C. B. (2014). A review of osteoporosis management in younger premenopausal women. *Women's Health, 10*(1), 59-77.
- McLeod, K. M., & Johnson, C. S. (2009). Identifying women with low bone mass: A systematic review of screening tools. *Geriatric Nursing, 30*(3), 164-173. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2008.07.003
- Mithal, A., Wahl, D. A., Bonjour, J.-P., Burckhardt, P., Dawson-Hughes, B., Eisman, J. A., . . . Morales-Torres, J. (2009). Global vitamin D status and determinants of hypovitaminosis D. *Osteoporosis International, 20*(11), 1807-1820. doi:10.1007/s00198-009-0954-6
- Moreira, L. D. F., Oliveira, M. L. d., Lirani-Galvão, A. P., Marin-Mio, R. V., Santos, R. N. d., & Lazaretti-Castro, M. (2014). Physical exercise and osteoporosis: Effects of different types of exercises on bone and physical function of postmenopausal women. *Arquivos Brasileiros de Endocrinologia & Metabologia, 58*, 514-522.

- Morris, C. A., Cabral, D., Cheng, H., Katz, J. N., Finkelstein, J. S., Avorn, J., & Solomon, D. H. (2004). Patterns of bone mineral density testing. *Journal of General Internal Medicine, 19*(7), 783-790. doi:10.1111/j.1525-1497.2004.30240.x
- Muslim, D., Mohd, E., Sallehudin, A., Muzaffar, T. T., & Ezane, A. (2012). Performance of Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool for Asian (OSTA) for primary osteoporosis in post-menopausal Malay women. *Malaysian Orthopaedic Journal, 6*(1), 35-39.
- National Institute of Health. (2014). What is osteoporosis? Fast facts: An easy-to-read series of publications for the public. Retrieved from https://www.niams.nih.gov/health_info/bone/osteoporosis/osteoporosis_ff.asp
- National Institute of Health. (2016). Vitamin D. Retrieved from <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/VitaminD-HealthProfessional/>
- National Osteoporosis Foundation. (2017). Risk assessment (FRAX). Retrieved from <https://www.nof.org/patients/diagnosis-information/risk-assessment-frax/>
- Nayak, S., Edwards, D., Saleh, A., & Greenspan, S. (2015). Systematic review and meta-analysis of the performance of clinical risk assessment instruments for screening for osteoporosis or low bone density. *Osteoporosis International, 26*(5), 1543-1554.
- Nayak, S., Roberts, M. S., & Greenspan, S. L. (2009). Factors associated with osteoporosis screening and recommendations for osteoporosis screening in older adults. *Journal of General Internal Medicine, 24*(5), 585-591.
- Nayak, S., Roberts, M. S., & Greenspan, S. L. (2011). Cost-effectiveness of different screening strategies for osteoporosis in postmenopausal women. *Annals of Internal Medicine, 155*(11), 751-761.

- Nishizawa, Y., Ohta, H., Miura, M., Inaba, M., Ichimura, S., Shiraki, M., . . . Fujiwara, S. (2013). Guidelines for the use of bone metabolic markers in the diagnosis and treatment of osteoporosis (2012 edition). *Journal of Bone and Mineral Metabolism*, 31(1), 1-15.
- North American Menopause Society. (2010). NAMS Continuing medical education activity; Management of Osteoporosis in Postmenopausal Women: 2010 Position Statement. *Menopause*, 17(1), 23-56. doi:10.1097/gme.0b013e3181cdd4a7
- Office of the Surgeon General (US). (2004). Bone Health and Osteoporosis: A Report of the Surgeon General. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK45513/>
- Palacios, S., Sánchez-Borrego, R., Neyro, J. L., Quereda, F., Vázquez, F., Pérez, M., & Pérez, M. (2009). Knowledge and compliance from patients with postmenopausal osteoporosis treatment. *Menopause International*, 15(3), 113-119.
- Papa, L. J., & Weber, B. E. (1997). Physician characteristics associated with the use of bone densitometry. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 12(12), 781-783.
- Papaioannou, A., Morin, S., Cheung, A., Atkinson, S., Brown, J., Feldman, S., . . . Josse, R. (2010). Clinical practice guidelines for the diagnosis and management of osteoporosis in Canada: Background and technical report. *Scientific Advisory Council of Osteoporosis Canada, Ontario*.
- Pecina, J. L., Romanovsky, L., Merry, S. P., Kennel, K. A., & Thacher, T. D. (2016). Comparison of clinical risk tools for predicting osteoporosis in women ages 50–64. *The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine*, 29(2), 233-239.

- Rubin, K. H., Friis-Holmberg, T., Hermann, A. P., Abrahamsen, B., & Brixen, K. (2013). Risk assessment tools to identify women with increased risk of osteoporotic fracture: Complexity or simplicity? A systematic review. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, *28*(8), 1701-1717.
- Rycroft-Malone, J. (2004). The PARIHS framework—A framework for guiding the implementation of evidence-based practice. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, *19*(4), 297-304.
- Saarelainen, J., Kiviniemi, V., Kröger, H., Tuppurainen, M., Niskanen, L., Jurvelin, J., & Honkanen, R. (2012). Body mass index and bone loss among postmenopausal women: the 10-year follow-up of the OSTPRE cohort. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Metabolism*, *30*(2), 208-216. doi:10.1007/s00774-011-0305-5
- Sale, J., Bogoch, E., Hawker, G., Gignac, M., Beaton, D., Jaglal, S., & Frankel, L. (2014). Patient perceptions of provider barriers to *post*-fracture secondary prevention. *Osteoporosis International*, *25*(11), 2581-2589.
- Sale, J., Gignac, M., Hawker, G., Beaton, D., Frankel, L., Bogoch, E., & Elliot-Gibson, V. (2016). Patients do not have a consistent understanding of high risk for future fracture: A qualitative study of patients from a *post*-fracture secondary prevention program. *Osteoporosis International*, *27*(1), 65-73.
- Schnatz, P. F., Marakovits, K. A., DuBois, M., & O'sullivan, D. M. (2011). Osteoporosis screening and treatment guidelines: Are they being followed? *Menopause*, *18*(10), 1072-1078.

- Schneider, D. L., Worley, K., Beard, M. K., Iannini, M., Ko, M., McCallum, J., . . . Steinbuch, M. (2010). The primary care osteoporosis risk of fracture screening (POROS) study: Design and baseline characteristics. *Contemporary Clinical Trials, 31*(4), 336-344.
- Schwartz, E. N., & Steinberg, D. M. (2006). Prescreening tools to determine who needs DXA. *Current Osteoporosis Reports, 4*(4), 148-152.
- Seo, S., Chun, S., Newell, M. A., & Yun, M. (2015). Association between alcohol consumption and Korean young women's bone health: A cross sectional study from the 2008 to 2011 Korea National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *BMJ Open, 5*(10), e007914. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2015-007914
- Shakil, A., Gimpel, N. E., Rizvi, H., Siddiqui, Z., Ohagi, E., Billmeier, T. M., & Foster, B. (2010). Awareness and prevention of osteoporosis among South Asian women. *Journal of Community Health, 35*(4), 392-397. doi:10.1007/s10900-010-9263-4
- Siris, E. S., Miller, P. D., Barrett-Connor, E., Faulkner, K. G., Wehren, L. E., Abbott, T. A., . . . Sherwood, L. M. (2001). Identification and fracture outcomes of undiagnosed low bone mineral density in postmenopausal women: Results from the national osteoporosis risk assessment. *JAMA, 286*(22), 2815-2822. doi:10.1001/jama.286.22.2815
- Stetler, C., Damschroder, L., Helfrich, C., & Hagedorn, H. (2011). A Guide for applying a revised version of the PARIHS framework for implementation. *Implement Sci, 6*(99), 1-10. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-6-99
- Stewart, T., & Ralston, S. (2000). Role of genetic factors in the pathogenesis of osteoporosis. *Journal of Endocrinology, 166*(2), 235-245.

- Tatsuno, I., Terano, T., Nakamura, M., Suzuki, K., Kubota, K., Yamaguchi, J., . . . Shozu, M. (2013). Lifestyle and osteoporosis in middle-aged and elderly women: Chiba bone survey. *Endocrine Journal*, *60*(5), 643-650.
- Teng, G. G., Curtis, J. R., & Saag, K. G. (2009). Quality health care gaps in osteoporosis: How can patients, providers, and the health system do a better job? *Current Osteoporosis Reports*, *7*(1), 27-34. doi:10.1007/s11914-009-0006-3
- U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. (2014). Vitamin D deficiency: Screening. Retrieved from <https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/Page/Document/RecommendationStatementFinal/vitamin-d-deficiency-screening>
- U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF). (2011). Osteoporosis. Retrieved from <https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/Page/Document/UpdateSummaryFinal/osteoporosis-screening>
- Unnanuntana, A., Gladnick, B. P., Donnelly, E., & Lane, J. M. (2010). The assessment of fracture risk. *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery*, *92*(3), 743-753. doi:10.2106/JBJS.I.00919
- Vu, H., Khan, N. C., Lam, N. T., Le, D. N., Nhung, B. T., Nakamori, M., . . . Yamamoto, S. (2005). Determining the prevalence of osteoporosis and related factors using quantitative ultrasound in Vietnamese adult women. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, *161*(9), 824-830.

- Watts, N., Bilezikian, J., Camacho, P., Greenspan, S., Harris, S., Hodgson, S., . . . Pollack, R. (2011). American association of clinical endocrinologists medical guidelines for clinical practice for the diagnosis and treatment of postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Endocrine Practice, 16* (3), 1-37.
- Watts, N. B., & Manson, J. E. (2017). Osteoporosis and fracture risk evaluation and management: Shared decision making in clinical practice. *JAMA*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.19087>
- Waugh, E. J., Lam, M.-A., Hawker, G. A., McGowan, J., Papaioannou, A., Cheung, A. M., . . . Jamal, S. A. (2008). Risk factors for low bone mass in healthy 40–60 year old women: A systematic review of the literature. *Osteoporosis International, 20*(1), 1. doi:10.1007/s00198-008-0643-x
- Weber-Rajek, M., Mieszkowski, J., Niespodziński, B., & Ciechanowska, K. (2015). Whole-body vibration exercise in postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Przegląd Menopauzalny Menopause Review, 14*(1), 41-47. doi:10.5114/pm.2015.48679
- World Health Organization. (2004a). WHO scientific group on the assessment of osteoporosis at primary health care level. *Summary meeting report*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/chp/topics/Osteoporosis.pdf>
- World Health Organization. (2004b). WHO scientific group on the assessment of osteoporosis at primary health care level. Summary Meeting Report Brussels, Belgium. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/chp/topics/Osteoporosis.pdf>
- World Health Organization. (2007). WHO scientific group technical report: Assessment of osteoporosis at the primary health care level. Retrieved from https://www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/pdfs/WHO_Technical_Report.pdf

- Wu, T. (2012). Hologic bone densitometry and the evolution of DXA. Retrieved from <http://www.hologic.ca/sites/default/files/white-papers/WP-00068%20HistoryDXA.pdf>
- Yang, Y., Wang, B., Fei, Q., Meng, Q., Li, D., Tang, H., . . . Su, N. (2013). Validation of an osteoporosis self-assessment tool to identify primary osteoporosis and new osteoporotic vertebral fractures in postmenopausal Chinese women in Beijing. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, *14*(271), 1-8. doi:10.1186/1471-2474-14-271
- Zhang, C., Ma, J., Chen, G., Fu, D., Li, L., & Li, M. (2015). Evaluation of common variants in CNR2 gene for bone mineral density and osteoporosis susceptibility in postmenopausal women of Han Chinese. *Osteoporosis International*, *26*(12), 2803-2810. doi:10.1007/s00198-015-3195-x
- Zhao, Y., Liu, Y., & Zheng, Y. (2013). Osteoporosis and related factors in older females with skeletal pain or numbness: A retrospective study in East China. *Journal of International Medical Research*, *41*(3), 859-866.
doi:doi:10.1177/0300060513483414
- Zofkova, I. (2011). Role of genetics in prediction of osteoporosis risk. *Vnitřní Lekarství*, *57*(1), 78-84.

APPENDIX A

Table 1

Table of Evidence - Osteoporosis Screening Tools among Adults

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
Assess the performance of screening tools in identifying those at risk for OP among postmenopausal Caucasians (McLeod & Johnson, 2009)	Systematic Review IV: 6 screening tools (SCORE, ORAI, OST, BW, OSIRIS, ABONE) DV: % Sen. & Sp of each tool	N = 33,628 (22 articles) Article Inclusions: Postmenopausal, Caucasians, Validated OP screening tools. Risk level based on threshold scores Setting: not stated	Threshold score of tools selected for determining level of risk for OP referred for DEXA. SCORE \geq 6 ORAI \geq 9 OST \leq - 1 BW < 70 Kg OSIRIS = +	Range of Sen. for tools across all studies: SCORE: 0.8 - 1.00 ORAI: 0.5 - 1.00 OST: 0.78 - 0.95 BW: 0.72 - 0.94 OSIRIS: 0.64-0.85 ABONE: 0.56-0.83 Range of Sp for tools across all studies: SCORE: 0.07-0.63 ORAI: 0 - 0.32 OST: 0.37 - 0.71 BW: 0.36- 0.53 OSIRIS: 0.39-0.69 ABONE: 0.48-0.84 SCORE: Sen \uparrow & Sp \downarrow in women > 65 as compared to women < 65. OST: Sen > 90% in younger women: useful tool in detecting those with low BMD. OST > OSRIS in identifying OP	OST = quick, easy & more consistent OST = developed in Asian women & validated in other ethnic groups & men. Other 5 tools = based on Caucasian women. SCORE = more complex tool OSRIS, BW, ABONE = need further validation ABONE = not relevant: estrogen use is not prevalent in this age group. Limitations: not stated

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
				SCORE & BW = lowest Sp. of all tools OSIRIS & ABONE = lowest performance in identifying low BMD	
				SCORE, ORAI, OST = more consistent for identifying BMD.	
Evaluate the performance of screening tools for DXA (S Nayak et al., 2015)	Systematic Review IV: 5 screening tools (OST, SCORE, OSTA, ORAI, BW) DV: % Sen. & Sp of each tool	108 articles included N = 60 - 21,063 Inclusion criteria: Age ≥ 18 Reported original data Sen and Sp values for each tool. Setting: 34 Countries	Threshold score of tools: determined OP or low BMD Standard thresholds: OST < 1 OSTA ≤ -1 SCORE ≥ 6 ORAI ≥ 9 BW < 70 kg	Postmenopausal women: Sen & Sp for each tool OST < 1: 89% & 41% (USA) OSTA ≤ -1 : 84% & 61% (Thailand) Qualitative review: OST < 6: 99% % 15% (Denmark) OSTA ≤ -1 : 29.9% & 91% (Chinese) OSTA < 2: 93% & 20% (Portuguese) SCORE ≥ 6 : 98.9 % & 5.7% (Belgian) SCORE ≥ 7 : 44% & 77% (Denmark) ORAI ≥ 9 : 100% & n/a (Portuguese) ORAI ≥ 11 : 3% & 98% (Denmark) BW < 70 kg: 88% & 43.6% (Portuguese)	OST, OSTA, BW = simple but performed as well as or better than more complex tools OST < -1: more appropriate for Asian pop Different thresholds may be needed to achieve adequate Sen in younger postmenopausal. Limitations: Heterogeneity of studies Mixed quality of the studies Publication bias

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
				BW ≤ 57 kg: 40% & 83% (Canadian)	
				Performance by age: OST, SCORE, ORAI, OSTA: Sen ↓ & Sp ↑ in younger vs. older women. BW: Sen ↑, same Sp in younger women	
Assess the effectiveness of screening tools in predicting major OP fractures among postmenopausal women (Carolyn J Crandall, 2015)	Systematic Review IV: 6 screening tools (FRAX, ABONE, ORAI, OST, SCORE, a tool based on SOF) DV: % Sen & Sp of each tool for prediction of low BMD and incident Fx	22 articles Included 14 focused on prediction of low BMD: N = 174- 18,315 8 focused on prediction of incident Fx: N = 1427 - 94,489 Inclusion criteria: the use of screening tool among postmenopausal women in US & Canada. Setting: US & Canada	Prediction of low BMD = if T score ≤ -2 or T score ≤ -2.5 Prediction of Incidence Fx = Major OP Fx during 10yrs of follow up. Standard thresholds for each tool: FRAX ≥ 9.3% OST ≤ -1 SCORE ≥ 6 ORAI ≥ 9 ABONE ≥ 2 SOF ≥ 5	Prediction of low BMD Range of Sen & Sp for each tool: FRAX ≥ 9.3%: 33% & 86% SCORE ≥ 6 or ≥ 7: 54% -100% & 13% - 72% ORAI > 8, or ≥ 9: 66%-100% & 28% - 79% OST ≤ -1 or < 2: 75%-95% & 40%-75% ABONE ≥ 2: 73%-83% SOF ≥ 5: 33%-76% Prediction of Incidence Fx for women age 50-64: Sen & Sp for each tool:	No tool persistently scored 85% or higher for SP. Simpler tools = performed better than more complex tools (FRAX) for prediction of low BMD SCORE & OST = Tools for identification of women 50-64 performed lower for those who will experience Fx. No tools persistently had sen > 90% for identifying prediction of BMD Some studies of SCORE & ORAI reported Sen > 90%

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
				FRAX \geq 9.3%: 26% & 83% OST \leq 2: 40% & 61% SCORE $>$ 7: 4% & 66%	Limitations: Small number of studies Non-standardization of thresholds scores across studies
				Sen of OST higher than FRAX	
Compare USPSTF strategy & 2 traditional strategies (OST & SCORE) in identifying osteoporosis (OP) screening women (Carolyn J. Crandall et al., 2014)	Descriptive cohort study IV: USPSTF (FRAX \geq 9.3%) vs. OST & SCORE strategies. DV: % high risk women met criteria for OP screening	Convenience sample of 5165 Inclusions: age 50-64, postmenopausal, free from serious medical conditions, no meds known to influence bone, & past DXA testing. 72% White 17% Black 8% Hispanic 3% Others Settings: Arizona, Pennsylvania, Alabama.	\uparrow risk women for OP measured by screening strategies. OP measured by DXA t -score \leq - 2.5 Low bone mass (LBM) measured by DXA -1 < t -score < -0.25 Screening strategies cut-off points: FRAX-score \geq 9.3% OST < 2 SCORE > 7	Women with OP: USPSTF identified 34% SCORE identified 74% OST identified 79% (all strategies p < 0.001) Women with LBM: USPSTF identified 18% SCORE identified 42% OST identified 49% (all strategies p < 0.001)	USPSTF strategy identified only 1/3 women with OP = better than chance alone & inferior to OST & SCORE in identifying women with OP Sp of USPSTF > Sp of SCORE & OST. Limitations: mostly White = not representative; FRAX did not include other cause of OP. Strengths? Large SS, systematic standardized data collection
Compare USPSTF & NOF strategy with BMD test in identifying OP screening adults	Descriptive cohort study of secondary data analysis	Convenience sample of 426 Inclusions: Adults age 50-75	\uparrow risk adults for OP measured by screening strategies. OP measured by DXA t -score \leq -2.5	Women 50-64: USPSTF screened 31% NOF screened 71% BMD screened 87%	Women 50-64: BMD test= overused. USPSTF (\geq 9.3 FRAX) > other strategies in \downarrow unnecessary screening

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
(Edwards et al., 2014)	IV: NOF strategy vs. USPSTF strategy DV: % of high risk adults met screening criteria	62.2% women 37.8% men 95% White 1% Black 2% Hispanic 2% Asian Setting: Arizona	NOF screening criteria: women ≥ 65 or men ≥ 70 ; or postmenopausal < 65 or men 50-69 with RF; or adults w/ Fx after 50; or adults w/risk of bone loss. USPSTF screening criteria: women ≥ 65 , or women < 65 with FRAX score $\geq 9.3\%$ BMD screening criteria: based on Gender, Age, & Risk Factors (low BMI, \downarrow calcium intake, \downarrow physical activity, smoker, alcohol use, parental Hip Fx Hx, \downarrow trauma Fx Hx, steroid use, or RA	($p < 0.01$) all 3 strategies identified similar % OP pts Men 50-69: USPSTF screened 13% NOF screened 79% BMD screened 15% USPSTF & BMD identified more OP pts than NOF Women aged 65+ & men 70+: BMD test is highly concordant w/ both strategies	Authors did not draw conclusion for women 65+ & men 50+. Limitations: Sample based off of secondary data analysis collected for different purpose; selection bias; sample not representative
Compare BMI alone with 5 current screening strategies in identifying early postmenopausal women w/OP (Jiang et al., 2016)	Descriptive cohort study IV: 6 screening strategies: USPSTF, OST OARI, SCORE, A RF-based approach vs. BMI DV:	Convenience sample of 445 Inclusions: age 50-64, postmenopausal & been scheduled for a DXA test. 95% White 2% Black 2% Hispanics 1% Asian/Others	\uparrow risk women for OP measured by survey and screening strategies. OP measured by DXA t - score ≤ -2.5 Telephone survey = age, weight, height, race, various RF, use of hormonal therapy (HT), concomitant medications, family & personal medical histories.	Sen & Sp: USPSTF: 24% & 83% OST: 79% & 56% OARI: 74% & 62% SCORE: 92% & 34% RF approach: 66% & 62% BMI: 95% & 38% All 6 strategies (p < 0.05) & LR - > 0.1	No strategies = ideal. USPSTF strategy = poorest among 6 strategies. Among 5 current strategies, SCORES = best. BMI $>$ other 5 in identifying OP cases <i>Limitation:</i>

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
	% high risk women meeting criteria for OP screening	Setting: Connecticut.	Screening strategy (cut-points for ↑risk or OP): USPSTF FRAX \geq 9.3% OST < 2 OARI \geq 9 SCORE \geq 6 RF-based approach \geq 1 RF BMI < 28		Sample at single institution & mostly White= not representative. Select population who already had DXA. BMI cut off point (< 28) = not validated.
Evaluate clinical utility of 3-step fracture risk screening program among young postmenopausal women (Schneider et al., 2010)	RCT IV: Intervention style: G1, G2, G3 DV: # ↑ risk women for OP	Convenience sample of 2839 Inclusions: Women age 50-64, ambulatory, never been dx'ed or treated for OP, able to complete questionnaires & under care of PCP 72% White 22% Hispanic 16% Others Settings: Western states	↑ risk women for OP measured by 3-step screening: RF, urine NTx & DXA. 9 RFs: ↓ trauma Fx at age > 50; BMI < 24; Wt \leq 125 lbs; Paternal hip Fx Hx age > 50, RA, use arm to stand from chair, current smoker, 3+ drinks/day, or steroid use \geq 30 days 3-step screening: G1=No RF & Usual care G2 = RF & Usual care G3 = RF + Intervention: If urine NTx < 50: Usual care If urine NTx > 50: Order DXA & Usual care All groups followed at 1,6,12 & 24 months via SAQs to compare OP	G1: ↓risk fx group = younger, heavier, Hispanic, in good health, non-smoker & < 3 drinks/day G2 & G3: ↑ risk fx groups = BMI < 24, previous Fx age < 50, Hx RA, or use arm to stand from a chair.	Risk assessment and urine NTx test = identifying ↑ risk women before ordering DXA test. <i>Limitations:</i> Selection bias, self-report bias; questionnaire may be misinterpreted. SS not representative The interval follow up results not well displayed

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Limitations & Notes
			perception & risks, & Tx compliance		
Address Sen & Sp of USPSTF criterion in identifying women with OP (Bansal et al., 2015)	Retrospective study IV: USPSTF (FRAX score) thresholds 9.3% vs. 5.5% Clinical RFs DV: % Sen & Sp of USPSTF (FRAX score) at detecting OP	Convenience sample of 464 Inclusion: Women age 50-64 who received DXA 96.8% White 0.9% Hispanic 0.6 % Black 1.7% Asian Setting: Minnesota	↑ risk women meeting ordering criteria for DXA testing measured by FRAX score threshold & clinical RF OP measured by DXA <i>t</i> -score ≤ - 2.5 Data & Clinical Factors abstracted from medical records & SAQs Criteria for DXA testing: Meeting FRAX thresholds or having ≥ 1 clinical RF (Hx osteopenia or OP, hyperthyroidism, celiac Dx, Aromatase inhibitor, Hx bariatric surgery)	464 DXA= 371 (79.8%) met criteria, 94 (20.2%) not met. Among 94 DXA classified as not meeting criteria = 13 (13.8%) had OP. Among 120 w/ OP, 14 (11.7%) classified as not meeting criteria Sen & Sp of FRAX (≥ 9.3%) threshold for DXA test: 37% & 74%. Sen & Sp of FRAX (≥ 5.5%) threshold for DXA test: 80% & 27% 59.7% DXA ordered by PCP 40.3% DXA ordered by specialists	USPTF FRAX (≥ 9.3%) = poor performance for OP detection in women age 50-64. A lower USPTF FRAX (5.5%) threshold score = ↑ Sen at detecting OP. PCP > specialists in ordering DXA Limitation: SS bias, not generalizable Retrospective sampling may ↓ evaluation of underutilization of DXA screening,

Note: % = percentage; # = number; ↓ = low; ↑ = high; ABONE = Age, Body, Size, No Estrogen; BMD = Bone Mineral Density, BMI = Body Mass Index, b/t = between; dr = doctor; BW = Body Weight; DXA = Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry; DV = Dependent Variable; Dx = diagnosis, FHx = Family History of, FN = Femoral Neck, FRAX = Fracture Risk Assessment Tool; FRPS = Fracture Risk Perception Study; Fx = fracture; G1,2,3 = group 1, 2, or 3, HRT = Hormonal Replacement Therapy; Ht = height; Hx = history; IV = Independent Variable, LBM = Low Bone Mass; LR(-) = negative likelihood ratio; n/a = not applicable, NOF = National Osteoporosis Foundation; NTx = urine N-telopeptide testing; OP = Osteoporosis; ORAI = Osteoporosis Risk Assessment Instrument, OSIRIS =

Osteoporosis Index of Risk; OST = Osteoporosis Self-Assessment Tool; PCP = Primary Care Physician; pt = patient; RA = Rheumatoid Arthritis, rec = recommendations; RCT = Randomized Clinical Trial; RF = Risk Factor; SAQs = Self-Administered Questionnaires; SCORE = Simple Calculated Osteoporosis Risk Estimate; Sen = Sensitivity; Sp = Specificity; SOF = Study of Osteoporosis Fractures; SS = Sample Size; Tx = treatment; USPSTF = U.S. Preventive Services Task Force; w/ = with, WHI = Women's Health Initiative; Wt = weight.

Table 2

Factors and Barriers Associated with Screening Rate for Osteoporosis

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Identify association of patient characteristics with physician screening recommendation & receipt of screening test for OP among older adults (Smita Nayak et al., 2009)	Cross-sectional mailed survey IV: patient characteristic DV: The number of high risk OP older adults receiving either physician screening recommendation or being screened	Convenience sample of 1268 Inclusions: Adults age 60 + 59% Female 41% Male 93% White 7% Others Setting: Pennsylvania	High risk older adults with receipt of dr. rec for OP screening or receipt of screening test as measured by 44-item mailed survey. 44-item mailed survey questionnaire = sociodemographic, knowledge of OP, risk factors, mobility, falls, health beliefs about OP, Hx OP, receipt of dr. recommendation, & receipt of screening.	66% reported screened; 22.6% had OP Women 65+ & men 70+: 50% received dr rec & 66% reported screened Receipt of dr. rec: More likely: female*** Whites*, FHx OP***, use arms to get up Less likely: ↑age or ↑Ht Not likely: steroid use >1 month***, Ht loss***, Hx ↓trauma Fx*** Heavy alcohol use ** or Smoker, or ↑Wt***) & ↓Ht Receipt of screening: More likely: female*** FHx OP***, Hx ↓trauma Fx***, or ↑Wt*** & ↓Ht*** Less likely: ↑Ht	Older adults = not 100% targeted OP screening. Individuals w/ ↑Fx risks = not recommended or undergo screening. Women >men received screening ↑ Physician awareness of individuals ↑ risk Fx or age 65+ for OP screening. <i>Limitation:</i> Self-report response bias; 1-month cut-off-oral steroid use vs. 3-month duration may be irrational; SS bias.

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
				Not likely: ↑age, Oral steroid use>1 month** White, ↑Alcohol use**, Smoker	
Examine the rate of DXA test is used in accordance with USPSTF recommendation (Amarnath et al., 2015)	Retrospective longitudinal cohort IV: OP risk factors DV: % of DXA test	Convenience sample of 60,899 Inclusions: Women age 40-85 At least one PCP or OB/GYN visit during the study year No DXA test in a prior year No prior OP Dx or medications for OP Setting: California	Incident DXA = DXA test completed during the study period OP risk factors: Age Smoking status BMI < 20 Steroid use Secondary OP RA Alcohol use Hx Fx	Incident DXA: ↑ with age in age group 50-74 then ↓ in age ≥ 75. ↑ in women with ≥ 1 OP risk factor ↑ with greater # of visits w/ PCP or specialists. ↑ with receipt of MMG Cumulative Incidence of DXA over 7-year period: who unscreened received DXA: Women ≥ 75: 43% Women 65-74: 58% Women 60-64: 59% with or without RF Women 50-59: 53% with RF and 46% without RF	Age, greater # of visits, receipt of MMG = strongly associated with DXA test. women ≥ 65: DXA underused Women < 65 without RF or with low RF: ½ DXA overused Low-risk women: should be screened before ordering DXA test Limitations: EHR records may be not accurate Did not include other OP risk factors such as premature menopause, oophorectomy Not generalizable

Purpose (Author, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results or Findings	Conclusions; Study Limitations & Notes
Determine whether women sent for DXA met the current guideline criteria (Schnatz et al., 2011)	Retrospective study IV: 2006 & 2010 NAMS screening guidelines DV: % women sent for DXA	N = 615 Inclusions: Women reached menopausal age ≥ 49 Women receiving DXA scan Setting: Connecticut	2006 NAMS screening guideline 2010 NAMS screening guideline	2006 NAMS screening guideline: 41% women who sent for DXA did not meet the criteria 2010 NAMS screening guideline: 40% did not meet the criteria Reasons for being sent for DXA: Age (64%) Previous bone Fx (1%) FHx bone Fx (8%) Low body Wt (1%) Unspecified RF (22%) Other reasons (21%)	Two out of every five women = inappropriately sent for DXA. Screening guidelines = not being followed Limitations: Inherent bias, recall bias Not generalizable Age (>49 y) = under average menopausal age (51 y)

Note. DXA = Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry; DV = Dependent Variable; Dx = diagnosis; FHx = Family History of; Fx = Fracture; IV = Independent Variable; MMG = mammogram; NAMS = North American Menopause Society; OB/GYN = Obstetrics/ Gynecology; OP = Osteoporosis; PCP = Primary Care Providers; RF = Risk Factor; USPSTF = U.S. Preventive Services Task Force; Wt = weight.

* $p \leq .05$; ** $p \leq .01$; *** $p \leq .001$

APPENDIX B
OSTA CHART

Excerpt derived from Osteoporosis Society (Singapore): *OSTA chart*: Now a test specially designed for post-menopausal Asian women. Retrieved from <http://osteoporosis.org.sg/osta-chart/>

APPENDIX C

FRAX CALCULATION TOOL

Country: **China** Name/ID:

[About the risk factors](#)

Questionnaire:

1. Age (between 40 and 90 years) or Date of Birth
Age: Date of Birth: Y: M: D:

2. Sex Male Female

3. Weight (kg)

4. Height (cm)

5. Previous Fracture No Yes

6. Parent Fractured Hip No Yes

7. Current Smoking No Yes

8. Glucocorticoids No Yes

9. Rheumatoid arthritis No Yes

10. Secondary osteoporosis No Yes

11. Alcohol 3 or more units/day No Yes

12. Femoral neck BMD (g/cm²)

Select BMD

Risk Factors:

Age	The model accepts ages between 40 and 90 years. If ages below or above are entered, the program will compute probabilities at 40 and 90 year, respectively.
Sex	Male or female. Enter as appropriate.
Weight	This should be entered in kg.
Height	This should be entered in cm.
Previous fracture	A previous fracture denotes more accurately a previous fracture in adult life occurring spontaneously, or a fracture arising from trauma which, in a healthy individual, would not have resulted in a fracture. Enter yes or no (see also notes on risk factors).
Parent fractured hip	This enquires for a history of hip fracture in the patient's mother or father. Enter yes or no.
Current smoking	Enter yes or no depending on whether the patient currently smokes tobacco (see also notes on risk factors).
Glucocorticoids	Enter yes if the patient is currently exposed to oral glucocorticoids or has been exposed to oral glucocorticoids for more than 3 months at a dose of prednisolone of 5mg daily or more (or equivalent doses of other glucocorticoids) (see also notes on risk factors).
Rheumatoid arthritis	Enter yes where the patient has a confirmed diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis. Otherwise enter no (see also notes on risk factors).
Secondary osteoporosis	Enter yes if the patient has a disorder strongly associated with osteoporosis. These include type I (insulin dependent) diabetes, osteogenesis imperfecta in adults, untreated long-standing hyperthyroidism, hypogonadism or premature menopause (<45 years), chronic malnutrition, or malabsorption and chronic liver disease.
Alcohol 3 or more units/day	Enter yes if the patient takes 3 or more units of alcohol daily. A unit of alcohol varies slightly in different countries from 8-10g of alcohol. This is equivalent to a standard glass of beer (285ml), a single measure of spirits (30ml), a medium-sized glass of wine (120ml), or 1 measure of an aperitif (60ml) (see also notes on risk factors).

Excerpt derived from the Centre for Metabolic Bone Diseases, University of Sheffield, UK: FRAX Fracture Risk Assessment Tools. Retrieved from <https://www.shef.ac.uk/FRAX/tool>.

FRAX Assessment Threshold without BMD for Major Fractures

Excerpt derived the International Osteoporosis Foundation: *What's your risk of fracture. Find out with FRAX*. Retrieved from <https://www.iofbonehealth.org/news/whats-your-future-risk-fracture-find-out-frax>

APPENDIX D
DATA COLLECTION TOOL

Weight (kg)	
Height (cm)	
BMI (kg/cm ²)	
Age (year)	
Previous Fracture	Y/N
Parent Fx hip	Y/N
Current smoking	Y/N
Steroid user > 3 months	Y/N
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Y/N
Secondary osteoporosis	Y/N
Alcohol user > 3 drinks/day	Y/N
Femoral neck <i>t</i> -score result	

LETTER FOR PERMISSION FOR USE OF DATA

DATE: May 1, 2017

TO: DONNA HONG TRAN

FROM: MICHAEL DAO, MD, Chief Executive Office

RE: PERMISSION FOR USE OF DATA

This memo confirms that I grant you permission to access and use patient data from our facility for your project, "OSTA vs. FRAX: Prediction of Osteoporosis among Vietnamese American Women Ages 45-64." The purpose of this retrospective study is to compare the differences in positive osteoporosis screens (according to DEXA) for the Osteoporosis Self-Assessment – Asian (OSTA) and Fracture Risk Assessment (FRAX) tools in a sample of up to 150 women. Both tools have been tested for sensitivity and specificity but never in a Vietnamese American sample.

It is understood that the data collection from electronic health records will only be used for the purpose of your project and will be securely kept in a password-protected file on your computer with additional security protection of a login password for the computer. Forms used during data collection will be housed in a locked file cabinet at your residence during the study, and when data has been entered into a database, will be destroyed. At that point, no patient identifying information will be included. Also, it is understood that this facility will be referred to only as "multi-practitioner primary care setting located in Orange County," leaving out the institution's name in any presentations and publications.

I am looking forward to the results of your project and sharing it with our colleagues.

Sincerely,

Michael Dao, MD